

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

D5.1 Blueprint workshop report

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Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document information

Grant agreement	101112800
Project acronym	eDNAqua-Plan
Project title	A Plan towards an eDNA reference library and data repository for Aquatic Organisms, navigating Europe towards the next generation biodiversity monitoring
Report title	Report from the Blueprint workshop
Deliverable number	None
Work package title	Data Standards, Data Linking & Compatibility
Work package number	5
Lead beneficiary	VLIZ
Authors	Katrina Exter (VLIZ), Emilie Boulanger (OBIS), Antonio Camacho (UVEG), Tim Collart (SSBE), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ), Carlijn Koole (SSBE), Oonagh McMeel (SSBE), Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC), Antonio Picazo-Mozo (UVEG), Saara Suominen (OBIS), Peter Woollard (EMBL-EBI)
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Due date	None
Submission date	2026/02/20
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	Report (not a formal deliverable)

Executive summary

This is a report on the Blueprint workshop held by Task 5.1 of eDNAqua-Plan in October 2025. The blueprint will be the output of deliverable D5.1 “Blueprint for a future eDNA digital ecosystem”, describing how to move from the current eDNA digital landscape to a more interoperable, standardised, and smoother future one. The participants at the workshop represented stakeholders from across the eDNA digital ecosystem: scientists, organisations, and infrastructure doing sample collection and storage, sequencing, bioinformatics, reference sequences and libraries, taxonomic classification and backbones, and DNA and biodiversity data publishing. On the first day of the workshop we presented our eDNAqua-Plan analysis of the current digital landscape and our proposals for a future landscape in which identified gaps in interoperability, standards, sharing, linking, publishing, and describing are plugged. The participants were grouped randomly to discuss three topic areas largely centered on these proposals, their feasibility, priorities, and enablers and bottlenecks. On the second day the participants were grouped into stakeholder categories so that topics specific to each could be discussed.

In Sec. [3](#) we summarise the discussions on:

1. Training, data literacy, data managers
2. Tools and templates
3. Encouraging the publishing of data
4. The role of scientific journals
5. ABS
6. Metadata
7. Biomonitoring
8. Machine-enabled data technology
9. Bottlenecks, enablers, and priorities

In Sec. [4](#) we group the discussions into:

- Data infrastructures (genomics and biodiversity)
 - Metadata
 - Provenance
 - Standards
 - Machine interoperability
 - Data flows
 - eDNA data in biodiversity repositories
 - Bioinformatics
- Reference libraries, bioinformatics, taxonomy
 - Reference libraries: curation, reference sequences, metadata, national reference libraries
 - Essential metadata
 - Curation, taxonomic information
 - Reference library service

- OTU/ASV tables
- Primers
- Bioinformatics metadata and standards
- How to ensure future success
- Biobanks, culture collections, taxonomic systems
 - Heterogeneity
 - Digital access and metadata
 - Legal compliance
 - Networks and collaborations
 - Taxonomic issues relevant to collections

As many of the discussion points and recommendations were common between and crossed over the different stakeholder groups, we consolidated these in Sec. 5, reframing as potential action items and recommendations to take on board at different levels by the different stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem:

- Guidelines and recommendations
- Metadata checklists or schemas
- Training and tools
- Standardisation and interoperability
- Metadata requirements
- AI/LLM and how it could be useful for us
- Publishing data
- Biomonitoring
- Provenance
- Bioinformatics
- Reference libraries
- Biobanks and culture collections
- Taxonomic systems

One very important take-home message is this: the stakeholders participating in this workshop are responsible for ensuring that (meta)data and software can be published (Findable and Accessible), that their (meta)data models ensure (meta)data Interoperability, that their systems expose those (meta)data Interoperable ways, and that they accommodate/provide metadata to ensure Reusability (provenance). The data/software creators, i.e. the scientists and the organisations that employ them, are responsible for publishing their digital objects in open access repositories, and for making the necessary efforts to create interoperable data and software, with provenance metadata. The eDNA digital ecosystem can be built by the stakeholders, but if these content providers do not contribute, then it will be an underfilled, underused ecosystem. Unfortunately, data literacy, a mindset that data publication is necessary (at least for publicly-funded research and monitoring), and tools and time to provide interoperable content, is sadly lacking among these content providers. This is a blocker to having a digital ecosystem that really serves the needs of science, scientists, and our environment.

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Abbreviations, acronyms, definitions

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ABS	Access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable Sharing of Benefits arising from their utilization
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BAGS	Barcode, Audit & Grade System, a software tool used in DNA barcoding and taxonomy research.
BBNJ	Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction
BGE	Biodiversity Genomics Europe project
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centres
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
Data	Refers to experimental or collected results (see also Metadata)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier, a unique alphanumeric string used to identify an online object, e.g. journal article, and provide a permanent link
DSMZ	German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH
DwC-A, DwC	Darwin Core Archive; Darwin Core
EC	European Commission
ECOSTAT	Environment Consolidated Statistical Tools
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EDMO	European Directory of Marine Organisations
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ENVO	Environmental ontology
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GeoBON	Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network
GGBN	Global Genome Biodiversity Network
GoaT	Genomes on a Tree
GSC	Genomics Standards Consortium
iBOL	International Barcode of Life
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
JRC	ECs Joint Research Centre
LDES	Linked Data Event Stream
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
LLM	Large Language Model
LOD	Linked Open Data
Metadata	Refers to both dataset discovery and description information, e.g. as found in dataset catalogues, <i>and</i> information included within

(text-based) datasets which give scope to the experimental/collected results.

MixS	Minimum Information about any (X) Sequence
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
PID	Persistent Identifier
QC	Quality Control
RDP	Ribosomal Database Project
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROR	Research Organisation Registry
SSBE	Seascope Belgium
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (formerly Taxonomic Databases Working Group)
URI/URL	Uniform Resource Identifier/Locator
UV	University of Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package(s)

1. Background to the workshop

eDNAqua-Plan is a three-year initiative aimed at creating a more harmonised and interoperable landscape for aquatic eDNA data across Europe. Bringing together experts and stakeholders from diverse fields, the project will assess the current state of the aquatic eDNA data landscape and develop a forward-looking, efficient, and sustainable vision – anchored in FAIR principles and aligned with global standards.

Ultimately, eDNAqua-Plan will deliver a technical blueprint for the future eDNA digital ecosystem, accompanied by an implementation roadmap designed in collaboration with key stakeholders.

In this context, Task 5.1 *Blueprint for future system(s)/workflow(s)* held a workshop over two half days in October 2025. This workshop was focussed on the [Landscaping report](#)^{R1} developed in Work Package (WP) 3, in which the current (mainly European) digital landscape around eDNA data was surveyed, gaps were identified, and a smoother, more interoperable and sustainable landscape was proposed. In the Blueprint workshop we followed up on that report, inviting the stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem in Europe and beyond to provide their feedback on the findings and proposals..

There is no formal deliverable associated with this workshop, however as it was so productive we felt it essential to synthesise the results into this report. The current proceedings report recalls the discussions and outcomes that took place during the two-day workshop. These proceedings do not necessarily reflect the eDNAqua-Plan recommendations, but capture the comments, ideas and recommendations provided by workshop attendants.

2. The workshop

2.1. Logistics

We invited over 320 individuals from over 140 organisations to the workshop, following the stakeholder list produced by eDNAqua-Plan (Milestone 1). These represented over 30 countries covering the domains of data infrastructures (aka data repositories), bioinformatics, biobanks and culture collections, reference libraries, taxonomists and taxonomy backbones, monitoring organisations and DNA-science organisations. The final list of external registrants (those who could attend and those who were interested but could not attend) was 123. Eventually, about 65 and 50, respectively, attended days 1 and 2.

Prior to the workshop, we prepared material for the attendees; these can be found in the [workshop public folder](#)¹ (the [README](#)² document is the starting point).

2.2. Workshop structure

The workshop started on Day 1 (October 8th) with a presentation of the landscaping report and how it was achieved. Some general discussion time ensued, before three breakout groups were formed to discuss three different questions related to the current landscape and recommendations to reach the future landscape. The groups were assigned randomly, as the intention was to get general rather than stakeholder-specific feedback.

On Day 2 (October 8th) we continued with three breakout sessions in which the attendees assigned themselves to one of three different stakeholder groups. Each group discussed the parts of the landscaping report and its recommendations that were relevant to their domains.

On both days we used Miro boards and recorded the sessions for later transcription.

2.2. Workshop outputs

The Miro board “stickies” were exported and organised into a [document](#)³ that was made available to the workshop registrants after the workshop. This was to allow for those who could not attend the workshop but did want to provide their own feedback, to do so via comments in the document. The presentations from the two days can also be found in the [workshop public space](#)⁴.

As well as these public documents, we also transcribed the recordings (using AI-transcription software) and took notes during the workshop: the notes and transcriptions are shared. All material was used to create this report.

3. General session: summarised feedback

On the first day the intention was to get feedback on the more overarching questions related to the current and future landscapes, and with the attendees mixed randomly they could also (potentially) learn from each other. In the three breakout sessions on Day 1, we discussed

¹ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1LRrFVjh_gQ_rAMJOr4tj4uIn7xuvYJV4?usp=sharing

²

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HeOhXQSdpdOUZx0NALc7P98qxRuE8ttzIH1k2Vu0d8k/edit?usp=sharing>

³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Sqlrwy_UI25CP7fIGOjQOBcxA-5U-g8Q6rh2cl1oKVU

⁴ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1LRrFVjh_gQ_rAMJOr4tj4uIn7xuvYJV4?usp=sharing

Breakout 1

- Of the mentioned aspects that *do not work well*⁵ in the current landscape: which do you dis/agree with and why?
- How would you suggest we *could tackle* these aspects?
- *Which of these are/are not a priority* for your organisation to tackle, and why?

Breakout 2

- Which are the *recommendations for a future landscape*⁶ that you think are the most/least important, and why?
- What do you see as being *enablers and bottlenecks* to taking up these recommendations?
- *Which of these are/are not a priority* for your organisation, and why?

Breakout 3

- What do you think of the suggestions on the *roles and responsibilities*⁷, and why?
- What do you see as being *enablers and bottlenecks* to the responsible parties being able to take up their responsibilities? Those of you who already perform these roles, do you have any advice?
- *Which of these are/are not a priority* for your organisation, and why?

While the focus of the workshop was on the eDNA data landscape, we are aware that many of the discussions and recommendations relate to issues around data in general.

N.B This document is a summary of the workshop discussions. Where we *respond* or *add* to a workshop point, we use *italics font*.

3.1. Training, data literacy, data managers

There were many comments regarding the need for training: in FAIR data generally, and specifically in FAIR data for the different domains in the eDNA digital landscape.

- Samples and sampling: related to metadata for fieldwork and experiments, and for subsequent processing.

⁵

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/170fkg8S3AGosPA7oCpLz1hKogUaL1nYiUjzq6ruokpY/edit?usp=sharing>

⁶

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/170fkg8S3AGosPA7oCpLz1hKogUaL1nYiUjzq6ruokpY/edit?usp=sharing>

⁷

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/170fkg8S3AGosPA7oCpLz1hKogUaL1nYiUjzq6ruokpY/edit?tab=t.8wjdzvxdw6d7>

- Reference library data: what and how to collect and share metadata for the reference sequences and identifications, and the use of those reference data within other datasets.
- Taxonomic data: how to expose taxonomic names and information and what metadata to collect and share, and the use of those taxonomic data within other datasets.
- Bioinformatics: formatting of outputs, what metadata to provide along with those outputs, how to FAIRify software.
- Biodiversity and omics data: how to format the data, what metadata to provide with the published data.
- What provenance metadata need to be collected and how should they be formatted and shared.
- Where and when to publish data, how to publish data, what data to not publish, and whether a DOI is necessary.

Special attention should be paid to those countries, organisations, and disciplines that lag with respect to data literacy, in particular where no data-centric courses are given as part of academic or technical training. The following were recommended as good and necessary practises:

- Stronger promotion and sharing of FAIR data management resources.
- Training of the scientists and technicians producing the data.
- Train the institutes to understand why data managers and data stewards are necessary.
- When budgets need to be cut, keep those studies that have comprehensive data management ensuring long-term benefits of the project and resulting data. A [recent analysis](#)^{R2} by the German Marine Research Alliance (DAM) stated this well: *“effective data management is an important prerequisite to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of research data”*.
- Scientists cannot be expected to be experts in their fields and also experts in data technology: it is the responsibility of their employers to provide data management training, tools, templates, and technologies. As a return, those institutes will produce much more useful, usable, and used data, which they can use to promote their importance in the domain (see a point in Sec. [3.3](#) about citation).

For each audience – whether individual scientists or complete universities – when providing training material, remember to “zoom out” to show the bigger picture: why is this important, what impact will it have, and what will happen if it is not done?

3.2. Tools and templates

Many comments centred around the desire for better tools and templates to help in the preparation of data for submission. While most data infrastructures do provide templates and some also provide tools, it is clear that somehow these are not finding

their audience in the expected way and/or they are considered to be difficult or time-consuming to use.

Scientists in the eDNA digital domain often create many different types of data which are to be published in different repositories with their differing tools and templates, and this could be one reason for the frustration: *too many differences*. In addition, where organisations do not place importance on the *publishing* of data, scientists often feel that they cannot take the time to tidy up their data and publish them.

While it is clear that different types of data do require different data and metadata templates, within the eDNA digital ecosystem more attempts to harmonise approaches could be made. For example, while there is a big overlap in the vocabularies that different data infrastructures use ([DwC](https://dwc.tdwg.org/)⁸, [MixS](https://www.genecol.org/pages/standards-intro.html)⁹, [ENVO](https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ENVO)¹⁰), there is less consistency in the way those are recommended to be used: in the ways to name common fields (times, places, agents and their roles, related publications), in the requirements with respect to how to enter values (string vs PID vs URI)¹¹, and in which values are mandatory or only recommended.

Most data in the eDNA digital ecosystem is some type of text file (CSV, TSV, the DwC-A components, FASTA, etc), and this fact lends itself well to the development of a set of universal templates which are standardised, which account for all possible entries, and from which different data infrastructures can pick and choose which parts to require for their data submissions.

An interesting suggestion was made to consider AI tools to assist in the standardisation of data before they are submitted to be published.

Several attendees expressed the desire for tools specifically to help scientists (i) collect metadata in an interoperable way that will immediately provide reusability (provenance), (ii) correct spreadsheets before they upload them to be published (i.e. carry out "plausibility" checks), (iii) format bioinformatics results into submission-ready data, (iv) and in particular, format data into DwC-A and validate that those are correct. Tools to do many of these already exist – a [DataHarmonizer](https://github.com/microbiomedata/DataHarmonizer)¹² from the National Microbiome Data Collaborative, GBIF's [DwC validator](https://www.gbif.org/tool/81281/gbif-data-validator)¹³ and its [metabarcoding toolkit](https://docs.gbif-test.org/mdt-user-guide/en/)¹⁴, FAIR eDNA metadata verifier ([FAIRe-fier](https://shinydev.it.csiro.au/live_apps/SukYeeYong/fairefier/fairefier/)¹⁵) and [FAIRe2MDT](https://github.com/FAIR-eDNA/FAIRe2MDT)¹⁶ from the FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) initiative, and many more. A desire was expressed not for *more* tools, but for *better* tools and for *an easier way to find them*: a

⁸ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

⁹ <https://www.genecol.org/pages/standards-intro.html>

¹⁰ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ENVO>

¹¹ A string is just an unformatted sequence of characters; a PID is a persistent identifier which is formatted following the data infrastructure's requirements; a URI is a PID that is also a web address and so globally accessible

¹² <https://github.com/microbiomedata/DataHarmonizer>

¹³ <https://www.gbif.org/tool/81281/gbif-data-validator>

¹⁴ <https://docs.gbif-test.org/mdt-user-guide/en/>

¹⁵ https://shinydev.it.csiro.au/live_apps/SukYeeYong/fairefier/fairefier/

¹⁶ <https://github.com/FAIR-eDNA/FAIRe2MDT>

central registry of tools was suggested. For example, given the growing number of [FAIR-related utilities](#)¹⁷, the working group is now developing coordinated R and Python packages to consolidate and manage scripts within a centralised framework.

eDNAqua-Plan feels that wider use of electronic lab notebooks (e-notebooks/LIMS) would be useful here – these being an app or portal in which scientists can enter their field, experimental, and analysis data. Many of these exist already. Those that also focus on producing FAIR data should have options to create interoperable and reusable metadata (e.g. using vocabularies, following provenance standards). In principle, it would be possible for “add-on code” to be developed (by anyone) to export their (meta)data in standards, formats, and following schemas that are suitable for the data infrastructures that publish the data. This would mean that users would not have to know e.g. how to work with DwC-A in order to produce DwC-ready outputs. If additionally those data infrastructures exposed their (meta)data requirements in machine-understandable ways (see Sec. [3.8](#)), then it would not only be easier to create these “add on codes” but also easier to keep them up-to-date.

3.3. Encouraging the publishing of data

It was agreed that one bottleneck to improving open, published, and FAIR data is the mindset still in place at least within the academic world: these activities are not generally considered important to advancing an (academic) career, or as significant outputs of an organisation. As a result, scientists often do not feel that they can take the time to learn how to publish FAIR data. **This is a mindset that needs to change before anything can be improved in the digital ecosystem.** This will require pressure from above more than from below: the academic career path must include data publications as a metric.

If scientists could better “advertise” the datasets that they (and hence their organisation) have contributed to, they are more likely to be able to gain credit for that work – a metric cannot be included in the academic career path if it cannot first be created. One way to develop this could be to credit datasets via [ORCID](#)¹⁸, which [does support data](#)¹⁹ as a type of “work” that can be accredited. Datasets are added to an ORCID when a data infrastructure makes the connection between their published data and the ORCID infrastructure, and via manual assignment of a DOI to a dataset by the data provider. We suggest that linking a published dataset, and its co-authors and contributors, to their ORCIDs should become part of the data submission process for *all* data infrastructures, and moreover that this is done as *automatically* (for all the data contributors) as possible. In the same vein, [ROR](#)²⁰ and [EDMO](#)²¹ (and similar catalogues of organisations) could be used similarly, providing a way for

¹⁷ <https://fair-edna.github.io/guidelines.html#available-scripts-and-tools>

¹⁸ <https://orcid.org/>

¹⁹ <https://info.orcid.org/ufaqs/what-work-types-does-orcid-support/>

²⁰ <https://ror.org/>

²¹ <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/>

institutions to see how much data they are producing. We note that EDMO does have such information – it links to the [EDMED](#)²² database; however from our quick check it is clear that EDMED does not list all datasets, likely because it is the responsibility of the organisations to (not forget to) update their contributions. A more automated method would be better.

Post-workshop, during internal OBIS discussions, the idea was floated to have a “d-index” to be the data equivalent to the “h-index” (a metric for evaluating the cumulative impact of an author's scholarly output and performance, and which is considered to be important within the academic career track).

Another suggestion was that the reproducibility of results, including the use of the data and pipelines published with the scientific publication, could be included as a general part of the peer review process, tackling both the reproducibility crisis as well as the requirement to publish data. However, will the voluntary peer review process be sustainable with this expansion? Some of the reviewable information, e.g. the DOIs and URIs of the datasets could easily be checked automatically and an automated report attached provided. A standardised (simple) workflow description template that can be filled in by the authors and which can be checked with automatic processes would also provide a useful resource for reviewers *and readers* (noting, however, that this will be technically demanding to make it easy for authors to fill in).

For data users, it is often difficult to discover any links between a sequence and related publications. This breaks the provenance chain, and makes it more difficult for data users to find additional information that may only be published in the scientific papers (an example given during the workshop was the primers used). Many journals do require information about datasets to be added to a data section, but this information is formatted for humans to read and understand, rather than machines (and so not accessible to search engines). Data infrastructures do not always provide metadata fields to add this information, but they would be very easy to add. Adding references to related publications is not high on the priority list when scientists submit their data, and even if these fields are made mandatory, at the time of submission the scientist may not yet even have a DOI for their paper. A way to work around this human reluctance and forgetfulness would be to have more automated processes for linking data and publications. This can only be achieved if the data infrastructures and journals expose the necessary information (e.g. the URIs of data used in the science published in the article) and harvest those information in machine-understandable ways, using web technology (see also Sec. [3.8](#)).

A comment was made that it does not seem to be possible for individual researchers to directly submit to GBIF or OBIS, or at least that it is time-consuming. Clearer information (short and visual) on the different ways that data can end up in GBIF

²² <https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/edmed/>

would help the community, and better support for those who may not have sufficient technical infrastructure at their disposal. .

For guidance and to enable more frequent data publishing, one suggestion was to consider a European-wide or even broader data brokering service. Brokers are an intermediary between the data submitters and the data repositories, and as such are a useful place to go to learn more about where to send your data. There are many data brokers: [GFBio](#)²³ and [COPPO](#)²⁴ and 11 others were mentioned. *Much of the data submitted to ENA goes via brokers, and ENA finds that their advantage is to provide the data-submission expertise that the scientists do not then need to have.* A potential advantage of using a data broker is that where they handle data with multiple destinations from one data submitter, provision of all the interlinks between these data could be ensured. Brokers are clearly a valuable part of the ecosystem, and a registry of data brokers in Europe would be a useful resource.

However, even data brokers need help navigating the eDNA digital ecosystem. They also need to know what standards, formats, vocabularies, and requirements will be put in place by the data infrastructures. They should be considered along with data infrastructures as an integral part of our digital ecosystem.

Ultimately, enabling the data provider to submit to one location, which then would flow to the different required databases in the eDNA digital ecosystem, would be a considerable improvement to the current situation. This location could be ensured either through brokerage, with the help of AI-tools, or through a new system built in connection with the different databases within the eDNA data landscape. One suggestion is to build a data-submitting workflow through OBIS and GBIF, that would also automate the submission to ENA at the same time, as well as registering the correct reference databases and taxonomic identifications.

3.4. The role of scientific journals

There were a few suggestions to solicit financial contributions from publishing houses to improve and then maintain the future ecosystem. While we believe that this is unlikely to happen on scale, certainly engaging the publishing houses in improving the landscape should be considered. Several publishing houses have their own or are linked to databases. eDNAqua-Plan believes that these are a good place to make the data included directly in the papers available, and they can also be a good place to archive data that otherwise fall out of scope of specialist repositories. But they should not be the first port of call to publish specialist data such as sequences (raw and any kind of processed), taxonomic lists (e.g. OTU tables), sample metadata, protocols: *specialist data should be published in specialised repositories.* Often the scientists submitting data just do it to get a data publication and so take the fastest route possible; but, if journals required that specific, recommended data repositories

²³ <https://submissions.gfbio.org/>

²⁴ <https://coppo-project.org/>

were used for specific data, then the “fastest route” would be via these specialist repositories anyway, addressing the argument from the data infrastructures that “scientists won’t submit data if the metadata requirements are stricter” (see Sec. [3.6](#)). *But this stick needs a carrot: acknowledgement, training, time, tools.*

A very interesting suggestion was made: journals could drop or reduce page charges if data are submitted to the recommended (specialised) data infrastructures.

We would like to recommend that scientific journals have metadata records for all their publications, as is the case with metadata for datasets. With this, it would be possible to add more information than is currently the case, one could add: semantically-annotated keywords, links to related datasets and publications, information on temporal and geographic range, related protocols, etc. This would significantly improve the ability to find publications related to data, and to find data from publications, in an automated way. The metadata associated with DOIs, e.g. CrossRef and DataCite, provide only some such information.

3.5. Access and Benefit Sharing

ABS (Access and Benefit Sharing) requirements in the context of international treaties, namely, the Nagoya Protocol and the BBNJ (Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction) agreement (to enter into force in early 2026) must be taken into account by those collecting samples in the field and utilising them. This includes many of the participants in the eDNA digital ecosystem. It is clear that there is still a lot of uncertainty, certainly on the side of individual researchers, as to what needs to be done. This is in particular because national regulations/procedures and the landscape in general vary a lot between countries. It is difficult and time-consuming to navigate a country's ABS regulatory procedure and adhere to them.

Having said that, there is a lot of documentation^{25,26} that can be found online on compliance with the Nagoya Protocol. In eDNAqua-Plan we will make recommendations as to how to deal with (meta)data in the context of ABS compliance. The workshop participants recommended that we also provide practical advice and examples that can be followed.

A recommendation to involve the GSC (and their MIxS standard) was made.

²⁵ See also <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44185-023-00013-7>

²⁶ Some examples: EMBRC developed two guides to ABS compliance:

- [Recommendations to marine biological resources, collections’ and users’ institutions](#)
- [A step-by-step guide to ABS compliance when utilizing marine genetic resources](#)

The CBD has developed guides about the Cali Fund - the multilateral mechanism for sharing benefits from the use of DSI - including a guide for databases.

- [Cali Fund : Guide for databases](#)

3.6. Meta(data) quality, quantity, standards

A common feedback was to have more mandatory metadata, and better standardised metadata. This refers to both the discovery and description metadata (e.g. as provided in metadata records of biodiversity catalogues and in BioSamples) and metadata as recorded within datasets (locations, times, measurements, etc). Anyone who has used data to do a large-scale analysis will know that having spatial, temporal, taxonomic, provenance, etc. metadata available and in a state where the information can be easily assessed is important, and very difficult to do *a-posteriori* if they are not provided with the information.

Wryly, we note that there was a strong request from data providers and users for more metadata to be provided, while at the same time the data infrastructures say that they often have great difficulties in getting the already-required metadata in the first place.

A key reason given by data infrastructures for not requiring more mandatory or more strictly-enforced (meta)data is that this will result in fewer data submissions: in their experience the data providers do not want to make the extra effort. For data infrastructures that deal with a wide range of data types (e.g. ecological repositories will include physical and chemical data as well as biological data), another limitation is presented by the difficulty of accommodating different domains with a single set of requirements. Finally, even the largest data infrastructures struggle with resources to carry out their work, and the curation of the (meta)data they receive. Making changes even just to the requirements on (meta)data means changing your data model and updating your database. While there is very little that is technically demanding about doing this, it does require human resources that may not be available.

For any data infrastructure to have excellent quality (meta)data, they need to be given more resources to employ curators and develop (semi)automatic QC tools, as well as to deal with their “historical” data, and/or the submitters of the data (the scientists) need to create interoperable and reusable data from the beginning of their research. As data literacy is generally too low for the latter to be a common practice (see Sec. 3.1), we recommend a far greater uptake of tools, for example e-notebooks/LIMS, to allow for more standardised (meta)data collection and publication (see Sec. 3.2). The quality of the data provided by the data creators is **the** key to the quality of the data published by the infrastructures. See Secs 3.1-3.3 for additional points that address this.

An interesting suggestion was to create exemplary (meta)data reporting standards (see also Sec. 5.1) and enforce them at the point where an eDNA paper is submitted to a journal. This could be tested in the [Environmental DNA](#)²⁷ and MBMG ([Metabarcoding and Metagenomics](#)²⁸) journals and perhaps with the Southern eDNA

²⁷ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/26374943>

²⁸ <https://mbmg.pensoft.net/>

society ([SeDNAS](#)²⁹), a PeerJ Hub. While the point of submission of a science paper is rather late in the data life cycle, this is a suggestion worth considering.

It was emphasised that any developments regarding standards, creating of recommendations, etc should be done with the data infrastructures: they have a central role in the eDNA digital ecosystem, and they need to take up any recommendations, otherwise it will be a wasted effort.

3.7. Biomonitoring

Monitoring of the environment and biodiversity is done to some extent by almost all countries, and in Europe we have the European reporting in addition to the national (e.g. the [European Environmental Agency](#)³⁰). Mandated data have to be deposited on a national level, but unfortunately these national-level repositories are often less FAIR and less open: if they were required to at least publish good metadata of all of their datasets, it would make it easier to find (and then request access to) their data. At the current time, very little eDNA biomonitoring is done in Europe, except in Sweden and UK.

Between academic research and monitoring work, there are differences in the field and lab work (who does it, what is done) and the data that are created (what is and is not considered important). The agencies doing the biomonitoring may not be research organisations and so their understanding of eDNA may be more limited. Biomonitoring field work and lab work are also done by companies, which have their own set of priorities that may not include treating data as a valuable object in its own right (as opposed to a means to an end). But we should encourage these organisations to also share their data. *Therefore, in our eDNAqua-Plan project deliverables, we should consider these other audiences.* For example, companies need straightforward workflows to explain how to format and publish data in the data infrastructures that are otherwise most heavily used by academic audiences. The people doing the field and lab work may not have a genomics background, and this should be borne in mind when writing the Blueprint and Roadmap (see also Sec. [5.1](#)). It is important for companies to know what will happen to their data, and this will encourage them to share their data. Good communication is important.

3.8. Using machine-enabled data technology

A good part of eDNAqua-Plan's Blueprint deliverable will be devoted to using web technologies to help standardise and expose (meta)data. This is not just to make those (meta)data more interoperable and accessible, but can actually also help to make data more manageable within data infrastructures themselves. Some of the

²⁹ <https://peerj.com/hubs/sednas/about>

³⁰ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en>

feedback at the workshop was related to this. For example, our recommendation is to link data directly to taxonomic information by the use of URIs, as opposed to just adding the taxonomic name as a string or as a PID³¹: PANGAEA and EurOBIS are examples of data infrastructure that do this well – adding URIs to their metadata wherever those can be harvested from the data they are given, with EurOBIS and OBIS requiring the use of [LSID](#)³² (Life Science Identifiers) for all taxonomic names in the data.

If data infrastructures were to expose all their data in machine-readable and machine-understandable³³ ways, then data sharing could operate without the need for human intervention, i.e. it would lower the cost of doing that work. If additional information such as their (meta)data models, used vocabularies, data formatting requirements, updates, were also shared in this way, then these information would be easier for machines – including developers of codes and e-notebooks – to find and use, again lowering the human resource costs and improving synchronisation between infrastructures. While this was not brought up by any of the attendees at the workshop, it was the reply to many of their questions, and the feedback was that this was a good idea. *Exposing such information using web standards – e.g. LOD (Linked Open Data) and LDES (LOD Event Stream) – would allow the data infrastructures to standardise the (meta)data sharing rather than having to standardise their databases:* It is not only expensive to re-engineer data systems, it would also be impossible to find one database structure that could accommodate all the stakeholders and data types in the eDNA digital ecosystem.

One interesting suggestion for dealing with “historical” (meta)data was made. When metadata requirements are updated, existing (“historical”) records will no longer be conformant in terms of the information present and the format of that information. Consider using tools (AI and non-AI) to correct/supplement those non-conformant metadata, e.g. by finding the semantics that are now missing (finding vocabulary terms for strings), or extracting the missing information from the related publications.

AI tools could also perhaps help to map different terms from vocabularies to each other, which would improve the understandability and reusability of those metadata and their linked data, in particular when searching for and combining data published by different data infrastructures and/or in different data formats.

3.9. Bottlenecks and enablers

During Day 1 the participants were asked to comment on the bottlenecks and enablers of the uptake of the recommendations made to reach the future landscape.

³¹ PID i.e. as an internal ID that is well-known *within* the concerned system but is not (machine) locatable outside of it

³² <https://www.lsid.info/>

³³ Machine-readable: a machine can open, process, and read (parse) and the digital object. Machine-understandable: the data includes semantic context so that a machine can additionally interpret and act on the information

We summarise those here, as well as highlighting some particular concerns that they had.

Concerns

- Many parties are still reluctant to share sequence data from their local biodiversity: how can they be sure this will not result in misuse of the data or misuse of nature? Clear guidelines for how this is dealt with by the data infrastructures is required, for example explaining how to embargo or hide particular elements of the data where they deal with sensitive species. Unfortunately, it is not really possible to deal with data misuse: while one should always issue a licence, it is very difficult to police the system.
- How to balance the need to have local reference databases with wanting to have a global access point? *We believe that the solution is to have both: local shares with global.*
- One concern raised was unacknowledged sharing. Methods should be put in place to ensure that when data are harvested, none of the important information is lost and the original citation and URI are always included. This can be done with modern data technology, but enacting it would have to be a community/stakeholder decision.

Bottlenecks

Short-termism

- Short-term funding, with a longer-term development time.
- Short-term thinking. Tools and codes that are developed in the context of a project/PhD are often “abandoned” after the author moves on to a new job. It should be mandatory that the organisations that fund this work ensure that they remain sustainable, or at least permanently findable and usable.

Lacking time, resources, workload

- The already existing workload and bureaucratic burdens represent a huge bottleneck for researchers to uptake virtuous data publishing standards. Data and informatics illiteracy in lower-capacity countries is generally higher, meaning the initial threshold is much higher.
- A lack of time to submit data: this is partly a mind-set change requirement, and partly a need for tools to allow FAIR data to be created as easily as not-FAIR data.
- The tussle between accepting only well-formatted and annotated (I and R of FAIR) data and allowing everyone to publish their data, results in either less data or less useful data. A suggestion for addressing this was to have a longer

chain encompassing more checkpoints: data creators → institutional data manager/steward → broker agent → database. Along this chain the curation status of a dataset would increase alongside the number of datasets that need to be handled, reducing the overall workload at each station along the way.

Incentives, mind-set

- Have in mind that there are countries with research cultures that place less importance on data. For some, data sharing is still perceived as something negative with the expectation someone else will undeservedly benefit from published data.
- A low incentive to data sharing, as the rewards for doing so are still more philanthropic than tangible.
- If nothing is imposed by the agencies funding the production of data, then the data will not be published in a FAIR manner.

A confusing ecosystem

- Data submission interfaces that are not intuitive to use, and documentation that takes too long to read.
- The current digital ecosystem is complicated, with different standards in different countries and often insufficient budget and time provided to do proper data management. This results in a lack of clarity on which data standards to use. See Sec [5.1](#) for potential mitigations, in the form of easier to find and read recommendations that are endorsed by the stakeholders.
- The fact that we are a large and disparate community with different "historical" ways of doing things: how can we try to include everyone?
- Differences in jargon between the different disciplines and the different data infrastructures data creators.
- We have a fragmented landscape to get from A (raw sequences) to Z (a type of biodiversity assessment).

Who will do the work?

- Many parallel and not necessarily coordinated efforts to establish guidance and guidelines by project consortia that are mainly rooted in research and ephemeral "products".
- Connecting databases (via adopting web standards for data sharing) is very interesting, but it depends on the collaboration of people involved in their maintenance: resources?

- Mapping between taxonomic backbones is time-consuming work, and there is no clear indication of who should do it. This diffusion of responsibility, and lack of funding to do it, is likely why there are many different examples.

Enablers

Build on existing resources, work together

- One could expand/work from existing metadata standards, e.g. ISO19115 and existing profiles of this standard (e.g. [MEDIN](https://medin.org.uk/)³⁴ discovery metadata in the UK) and vocabularies (e.g. [NERC Vocabulary Server](https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/)³⁵).
- Work together to build the (meta)data standards, templates, and specifications.
- Data champions within organisations to maintain efforts.
- Connect all the initiatives developing country-based reference libraries to agree upon common grounds while allowing for their own idiosyncratic differences.
- Leverage existing international efforts in this area (e.g. [FAIR eDNA](https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html)³⁶, aka FAIRe).
- Communication to the public and policy makers on the importance of sustained eDNA datasets.

Incentives, rewards

- Enable efficient citation and tracking of data (re)use to document the impact of datasets.
- Sustained, government support for the generation of public datasets.
- Demonstrate innovative projects/outcomes that leverage FAIR data, to help show what FAIR and open data can do.
- Data papers and data in repositories should be viewed as high impact outcomes.
- Reviewing the data should be a mandatory part of peer review (and recognised as such by the editors). *(Reviewing is often done on a voluntary basis by researchers, adequate rewards for this extra work, or the employment of technical reviewers, should be considered.)*
- Research institutions should also be responsible for rewarding the publishing of data. For example, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences provides bonus funding for high-rank publications, but could additionally enforce rewarded standards for FAIRness, data publishing, etc.

³⁴ <https://medin.org.uk/>

³⁵ <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>

³⁶ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

- The funders should encourage and positively view publishing data as a “high impact” outcome of the projects, in addition to publications. Acknowledge good data sharing as equal to publication sharing (in the eyes of funders and employment panels).
- Science is innovative, and data can be seen as just baseline information whose outcomes/stories are not so clear. Should we stop comparing ourselves in the digital ecosystem directly to the academic/scientific world, and make our systems/rewards different?
- Reduced or no publication fee for articles with FAIR and open access (meta)data. *This could be an addition to the Gold Open Access system, so that the funding body makes the associated costs eligible if the articles are accompanied with FAIR and open access (meta)data.*
- In some countries it is necessary to report on the impact that you (a company, an organisation) are having on the environment and climate: publishing the data collected to measure this should be mandatory, and credits for doing so should be offered.
- Having standardised funder IDs published along with datasets, allowing them to receive measures of their impact. This could also be useful to encourage public companies to share data, especially if formal acknowledgement of that impact were taken up. The same advice for projects (whether funded by Europe or others): these often create a lot of data and that should be considered an asset of the project participants and their organisations, and the funding agencies.
- Data should be looked at as valuable as a piece of equipment that is bought for the lab.

Resources, technologies

- Guidelines for standards of data publication should be inclusive (i.e. translated into local languages), so everybody has the opportunity to collaborate.
- The establishment of community efforts/events can be an enabler – “hackathons” to help the less-knowledgeable stakeholders.
- Investment in data brokerage as mediators between data creators and data archives. This can be seen as a safeguard against data illiteracy.
- Fewer, but well maintained user-friendly tools, rather than a multiplication of tools.
- Focus on machine-readable and -understandable web standards, while noting that there is definitely a need for additional user-friendly data publishing tools.
- Data stewards employed by organisations creating the data, and have them interact with each other over Europe, between institutions and agencies etc.
- Better distribution (better findability) of information on data publishing and other workflows.
- Early training of students through university curricula.

- Publishers can be important enablers for standardising data publishing, through imposing minimum standards, by giving publicity for exemplary publishing pipelines, offering financial support for training, and encouraging reviewers to check metadata/data standards. They should also have guidelines for reviewers to check whether the data has been published.
- Citation of datasets should consider them not only as a whole dataset, but where any part of them are included in aggregated data. Such aggregated citation should be common practice and exported as metadata along with any aggregated data provided by data infrastructures (as some do already). In GBIF they aggregate citation scores based on re-use of datasets.

3.10. Priorities

On Day 1 the participants were asked which recommendations were of higher priority than others. Here we summarise the feedback.

The highest priority should be given to the following

- Providing guidance documentation that is user-friendly for all parts of the ecosystem, including best practices for sharing reference databases and taxonomic backbones, etc.
- Training and data managers.
- Pushing funders and journals to require proper and rich data sharing and acknowledge data publications. Funders should not just require this: they should also check on and enforce it. Where they do not have the expertise or resources to do this “manually”, automated tools to check on the presence of metadata and data in funder-recommended repositories could be a workaround.
- Pushing funders to provide resources to allow for sustainable practices.
- For agencies that fund data production (water agencies, ministries, Horizon Europe, etc.): they should understand that they have a key role to play in making data FAIR by imposing good minimum requirements for data.

Next are

- Machine-readable web standards and exposure of metadata (URI vs string), and consistent use of standards.
- Richer metadata, mandatory metadata, curated metadata, corrected metadata.
- Reference libraries: to be more interoperable, have better standardisation, and give credit to the curators and creators when the reference libraries are used. This second point applies additionally to all types of data.
- Working together as a community to develop the future landscape and to develop sustainable publishing pathways.
- User-friendly tools.

- Taxonomic assignment tools that can act across many different independent reference databases.
- Making data creators and holders aware of the benefits of data sharing.
- Providing and supporting richer metadata templates for data submission and bioinformatics outputs.
- Open-access protocols.

Finally, as lowest priority we have

- Standards to be imposed from above.
- Discouraging publishing in generalist repositories.
- Having more mappings between vocabularies.
- Requiring more of the bioinformatics outputs to be published: concentrate on publishing good code metadata and provenance.

The comments from some of the data infrastructures at the workshop concerning their own priorities are:

- The [DSMZ](https://www.dsmz.de/)³⁷ focuses on very high-quality and user-friendly databases (for data access).
- The British Oceanographic Data Centres ([BODC](https://www.bodc.ac.uk/)³⁸) prioritises ensuring linkages between sequence data held in specialised repositories (e.g. Genbank) and environmental data collected from the same samples held in their own database. BODC's priority is in participating in discussions on controlled vocabularies and metadata/data standards.
- Most of the bullets in [this Day 1 document](#)³⁹ are priorities for GBIF. They now have specific funding to prototype a repository of reference libraries, where creators of reference databases can share and update their products in a standardised format, and receive citation and annotation metrics.
- GBIF sees themselves as “just” a data infrastructure that allows data to be shared. They do not impose a strong(er) enforcement of specific metadata as they do not see that as their role: this will limit the data being published. It is up to the end user to decide if there is enough metadata to use any particular data in their analysis.

4. Stakeholder-specific sessions: summarised feedback

On Day 2 we continued with three breakout sessions in which the attendees assigned themselves to one of three different stakeholder groupings:

³⁷ <https://www.dsmz.de/>

³⁸ <https://www.bodc.ac.uk/>

³⁹

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/170fkg8S3AGosPA7oCpLz1hKogUaL1nYiUjqz6ruokpY/edit?usp=sharing>

- A. Data infrastructures, data publishers, data creators (of eDNA and biodiversity data)
- B. Reference libraries, bioinformatics, and taxonomy (with respect to how taxonomy is included in other data sets)
- C. Biobanks, culture collections, and taxonomy (with respect to scientific concepts around taxonomy)

Each group discussed the parts of the Landscaping report and its recommendations that were relevant to their domains: for details of the particular discussion points, see [this day 2 documentation](#)⁴⁰.

N.B This document is a summary of the workshop discussions. Where we *respond* or *add* to a workshop point, we use *italics font*.

4.1. Data infrastructures and data publishers: omics and biodiversity data

With “data infrastructures” we include organisations that have data catalogues, repositories, or archives via which data are published, and data brokers. “Data publishers” are individuals or organisations that publish data they have created themselves. “Data” includes any types of omics data, but most commonly sequences and bioinformatics outputs, and biodiversity, environmental, etc data.

We had representatives from these groups at the two breakout A sessions on Day 2. These sessions were centered around the recommendations made by eDNAqua-Plan’s landscaping exercise concerning:

1. Metadata
 - a. Expanding the required metadata, and standardising those metadata
 - b. Requiring more semantically-annotated metadata
 - c. Metadata “checklists/schemas”: listing what (meta)data need to be present for a dataset to be fit for some particular purpose
2. Stronger requirements on provenance (meta)data
3. Data formatting – data standards and templates
4. Machine-interoperable data and metadata
5. Data flows, from local to global
6. Particular issues with eDNA data in biodiversity archives
7. Interoperable and open bioinformatics outputs

⁴⁰

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bjiZgFHgStKw8ol8tsbjbislmhj8oecB8F56h1kg_8/edit?usp=sharing

The day 2 [workshop preparation document](#)⁴¹ contains more detail on the proposed discussion points.

N.B For this report: “metadata” refers to both dataset discovery and description metadata as found in dataset catalogues, *and* metadata included within (text-based) datasets that gives scope to those experimental/collected results, while the results are what we call “data”.

4.1.1. More mandatory and faster correcting of metadata

Regarding metadata:

- Where mistakes in (meta)data are identified after they are published, there should be an easy and well-advertised method for collecting that feedback and making the corrections in a timely manner. Making corrections will require resources for the data infrastructure. A likely bottleneck here will be when the data provider is no longer contactable or does not respond to requests; a work-around could be to add the corrections to a separate section in the metadata. This same suggestion could apply to data, since making unilateral corrections to *data* is a much more serious prospect. This is the approach taken by ENA via the [Clearinghouse](#)⁴²; anyone is able to provide third party curations to any ENA/INSDC object irrespective of whoever owns it; alternatively, this can be done via [ENA directly](#)⁴³ for your own submitted data (although for both, the process could be made more simple)
- One participant had been struggling for two years to get some simple, and clearly incorrect, definitions in a MIxS checklist corrected by GSC. [MIxS issues can be reported](#)⁴⁴, but the response can be tardy.
- There are discrepancies in the minimum metadata required between the different but related data infrastructures (the example given being GBIF and OBIS), and this was highlighted as a source of confusion for data submitters. It was pointed out that eDNA scientists often have to submit different types of data (sample metadata, sequences, bioinformatics outputs, and then biodiversity results) to different data infrastructures: a single place to find all the necessary information could help here (see also Sec. [5.1](#)).
- While there was a demand for more mandatory metadata, there was also an acknowledgement that this requires resources from the data infrastructures. Where metadata requirements change, data models, databases, documentation, and entry forms or templates have to be changed.

⁴¹

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bjiZgFHgStKw8ol8tsbjbislmhoj8oecB8F56hkg_8/edit?usp=sharing

⁴² <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/annotation.html>

⁴³ <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/update/metadata.html>

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/GenomicsStandardsConsortium/mixs/issues>

- There were many comments about the lack of PCR primer data and/or information provided in ENA and reference libraries. It is important to know what primers were used and whether they were trimmed from the submitted sequences. This should be a mandatory metadata field, and/or it should be possible to upload the primers as “associated data”. Note that where primers are published in non-open access journals, it is not sufficient to give a citation to those articles. BOLD requires primer codes to be provided together with their sequences, and hence for datasets appearing in both, there is the possibility that ENA could harvest the metadata from there. When harvesting data from ENA, MGnify makes the effort to infer the primer sequence (using the EBI [PIMENTO](#)^{R5} tool), but this does not work for all sequences (and should not be necessary). Could such a tool be used to add primer information retrospectively to “historical” records?

Fields that are currently not mandatory everywhere and which were mentioned as being important were:

- PCR primer information (sequences) *provenance, data re-usability*
- Data contributors as well as data creators/owners *acknowledgement*
- Related publications and related datasets *acknowledgement, data re-usability*
- Latitude and longitude *provenance, data re-usability, ABS compliance*
- “And pretty much everything on the [FAIRe](#)⁴⁵ checklist classified as mandatory” (see Sec. [4.1.3](#))

Note that some of these fields have become mandatory for data infrastructures in the last years, but “historical” data (all data submitted before any change takes place) may not have these information. An interesting suggestion to use AI to add some of the missing information was made: see also Sec. [3.8](#). (Although, as with any suggestion involving AI/LLM, one should balance their use against the demand on natural resources that they make.)

GBIF is one of the largest providers of global biodiversity (meta)data. However, they do not see their role as being one to (more strongly) mandate what metadata should be provided: as described in Sec. [3.10](#), GBIF sees themselves as “just” a data infrastructure that allows data to be shared. Stronger metadata requirements will result in fewer data submissions. Instead, it is up to the end user to decide if there is enough metadata to use any particular data in their analysis. OBIS, one of the largest providers of ocean biodiversity data, takes a slightly different point of view, placing stricter requirements on the quality of the metadata. *It is possible that users of the data from these two data infrastructures do not understand these differing points of views, and making that more clear, up front, would therefore be useful.*

A point was made that providing the information about what metadata are mandatory is useful not only to data providers but *also* data users, and so the place that this

⁴⁵ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

information is given in the data infrastructure's documentation should be somewhere that data users, not just data submitters, will look.

The response that making requirements for data submission stricter would result in fewer data submissions is one made by many data infrastructures at the workshop. *It would be worth checking what it is that is the cause of this: is it the fact of having to include more metadata, or the fact that the data formatting and submission process is already complicated enough? For the second, would better guidelines, intuitive submission interfaces, tools to format data before they are submitted, and tools to make data FAIR as they are collected (and so they are then easier to reformat), overcome that barrier?*

A final discussion was around the question of producing "checklists/schemas" to identify data that could be used for a specific purpose. This has become a potential action item for eDNAqua-Plan, see Sec. [5.2](#) for more on this topic.

4.1.2. Provenance (meta)data

The "Provenance" of data is the record of what has been done to obtain those data. Ideally. For eDNAqua-Plan, provenance allows someone else to completely recreate and experiment and reproduce data, to be able to repeat all the steps, from any collection of material samples, through processing, storing, shipping, "extracting" the data, and all subsequent data processing stages. This should be provided either within dataset description metadata or as a separate, formatted and standardised file that is included as part of a dataset. Currently, most scientists and data infrastructures consider provenance to be satisfied with less information: dates, locations, (at least the names of) protocols, names of bioinformatics platforms and codes, names of the types of instruments used, but not also the versions, settings, IDs, URLs to the software and open access protocol documents, sample and event IDs, agents, and with no mandatory use of controlled vocabularies or that direct links to preceding provenance (meta)data are given. Some data infrastructures have a "methodology" section in their metadata, however this is for unstructured text with the amount of information provided left for the data submitted to decide themselves. Some data standards (DwC) and checklists (MlxS) include fields for provenance information, but these information are often only recommended, not mandatory, and in any case do not provide a full provenance trail.

Considering that the different types of data along the data trail are published in different data infrastructures, this breaks up the accompanying provenance trail. In this scenario, it is not only that each dataset needs its own provenance, but it needs to link to the provenance of the preceding dataset, and this is currently done imperfectly.

To include the full provenance would clearly require an update of the databases, procedures, and user interfaces of the data infrastructures, which would require financial and human resources. During the discussions, it was pointed out that providing templates to allow the scientists to collect and then share provenance information as metadata files that could be uploaded along with data files, may be easier for the data infrastructures to implement. Unfortunately, this would be an additional burden on the scientists, especially as provenance is on the whole overlooked and so not part of standard practices. E-notebooks/LIMS, in which experimental (meta)data are recorded, could export provenance information following templates relatively easily. Even so, it is likely that only the better resourced organisations and projects would do this. The impression we got from the discussion during this session is that improving the provenance metadata requirements for the data they publish is not a high priority.

Participants' suggestions regarding provenance largely focussed on the lack of (accessible) protocols describing the field and experimental work and the bioinformatics analysis. *This is one aspect of provenance that could be improved relatively painlessly, as most data infrastructures do already have fields for and recommendations about protocols: if these fields were made mandatory, and if it were mandatory to either include a full description of the procedures or a URI/DOI to a protocol document, that would immediately improve the reusability and trustability of the data.*

It was pointed out that publication of protocols should be considered as part of the metrics that scientists are judged on within the academic career track. This would encourage their publication.

A few specific questions on protocols were raised. The following advice was given:

- As long as the protocol is accessible (can be found online and is open access), any deviations that were followed can be added to the provenance metadata alongside that protocol URI/DOI.
- Protocols that are very short can be written directly into the provenance metadata, rather than needing to be published separately.
- At the present time, protocol documents will always need to be read by humans. While protocols can be made machine-readable – see e.g. the [BeBOP](https://github.com/BeBOP-OBON)⁴⁶ initiative and RO-crates (e.g. [RO-Crates for biodiversity](https://esciencelab.org.uk/bge-ro-crate-profile/)⁴⁷) – it is currently not feasible to make a protocol *completely* machine-understandable: to describe every single step in a semantically-rigorous way would require vocabularies to annotate every device, instrument, chemical, cleaning cycle, filter size.....Therefore it is acceptable to assume that humans will be doing the “understanding” part.
- A “protocol” is usually considered to describe physical activities, but the methodologies included in code/workflows that are used to produce or process

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/BeBOP-OBON>

⁴⁷ <https://esciencelab.org.uk/bge-ro-crate-profile/>

data, and the inputs to those software, should also be considered as a type of protocol. These information should be treated in the same way: the codes should be accessible, the inputs to the codes should be documented. (A further discussion on bioinformatics is summarised in Sec. [4.2.8](#)).

- MlxS (and similar) checklists are different to provenance: while they do allow for the documenting of much information, they do not provide a repeatable history of what was done to create the data being archived. However, many of the fields in these checklists, as well as those in [FAIRe](#)⁴⁸, are provenance information.

4.1.3. (Meta)data standardisation, standards, and templates

Standards and standardisation

Many comments were made about the standardisation of the metadata provided with and in data, on data standards and how to use them, and on templates to help scientists submit good (meta)data.

- There was an expressed desire to have more standardisation of metadata between data infrastructures: in the way the metadata fields/column names (in CSV templates) are written, in what is recommended with respect to the content to be provided, with the given definitions and examples, and even with the particular vocabularies and ontologies used. This is a source of confusion in particular for data creators publishing to different data infrastructures. Clear, and common, guidelines would be helpful. Particular mention was made of the MlxS terms (which are set by the GSC).
- eDNAqua-Plan recommends that vocabulary terms are given in the (meta)data as URIs as well as strings: the metadata exposed on a webpage for a human to read can use the string, while the metadata written into files to be downloaded (e.g. for provenance of the related dataset) or for machines to read should have both. It was agreed by the participants that this is a good idea, however it would require good guidance and examples. *Making those vocabulary terms selectable from pick-lists or drop-downs within the metadata web forms would be a way to make this easy to do for the data providers. Where metadata are rather to be uploaded via a template file, then links to the chosen vocabularies and examples of how to enter the values in the template should be given. For some examples of how this could work, see the checklists of [ENA](#)⁴⁹ and [NCBI](#)⁵⁰. An example of a solution is the [OBIS Extended Measurement or Fact tables](#)⁵¹, where both the term and the URI for the vocabulary are recorded.*

⁴⁸ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

⁴⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/docs/packages/>

⁵¹ https://manual.obis.org/format_emof.html

- Related to this point, ENA (and by extension, all other data infrastructures) should not allow free text for ENVO terms, but force use of the URI (or at least the full PID) instead. At a technical level, for metadata this could be eased by the use of a selection tool within the input form.
- It is necessary that any metadata standardisation achieved between data infrastructures can be maintained, to ensure that the latest version is always followed by all organisations in a timely manner. *eDNAqua-Plan will explore the feasibility of the suggestion to have one place where the various standards used by the stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem is documented, including how, when, where those terms should be used and to issue updates and versioning information, and the data infrastructures would take their cues from there. Differences, and their reasons, adopted by different infrastructures could also be documented there (there are valid reasons for some differences to occur). (Note that eDNAaquaplan will not create such a place, rather we strive to provide recommendations.)*

After the workshop, we checked for examples of differences in dealing with the (otherwise same) metadata:

- In GSC at the NCBI: title="geographic location (country and/or sea,region)" structured="geo_loc_name", but in ENA "geographic location (country and/or sea)" and "geographic location (region and locality)"*
- In GSC at the NCBI: title="geographic location (latitude and longitude)" structure_name="lat_lon", but in ENA: "geographic location (latitude)" and "geographic location (longitude)".*

In both examples, the GBIF/DwC metadata structure follows that in ENA, but as well over half of INSDC data comes through NCBI, such inconsistencies really matter. Note that DwC is based on an older version of MlxS (not the current) and there is a drift over time with definitions and even occasionally terms.

(Meta)data interoperability relies on the use of standards: what format is used and how the data are organised within that format. The eDNAqua-Plan landscaping recommendation is to use common formats across the ecosystem as much as possible, and to organise the data within those formats in a standard way: common naming of terms, use of common vocabularies, common formatting of the data in the file, shared examples, common expectation of what terms are mandatory and how to write the values into those terms (e.g. string vs URI). The participants considered it important to not create new standards, but use those that are already in common use over the ecosystem more consistently and interoperably.

Some data formats that are already common are DwC-A, FASTA and FASTQ, and these are also fairly well standardised (although FASTA and FASTQ still have some improvements that could be made: see comments in Sec. [5.4](#)). For metadata, we have the standards EML (a schema), and MlxS and DwC (vocabularies). For data

packaging we have [RO-Crate](#)⁵². Most ecologists and eDNA users are likely more familiar with tabular metadata formats (e.g. spreadsheets); therefore, this format has been adopted in, for example, the MDT input structure and the FAIRe templates. For these, however, the way the information is packaged within the formats is not standardised across the digital ecosystem, and *this* is a particular recommendation of eDNAqua-Plan.

Furthermore, as formats and standards will change with time and technology, we recommend that when these changes happen, all stakeholders in the ecosystem communicate about how they are dealing with those changes, and work together to maintain synchronicity and standardisation.

The ultimate aim of data standardisation is simplification and interoperability. With this, similar types of data from different infrastructures could be more easily combined, different types of data within the eDNA digital ecosystem could be more easily compared, and it would be more simple for data providers to navigate the “data format ecosystem”. On this we had agreement from all participants, but some concerns were mentioned.

- While DwC-A (data) and DwC (vocabulary) are widely used standards in the biodiversity digital ecosystem, not all data infrastructures use these and so they cannot readily connect their data into this pathway. To map their data onto these requires resources from those data infrastructures. With DwC, one can call on the [TDWG](#)⁵³ (who maintain the standard) resources, but each data infrastructure imprints their own signature on their DwC and that also needs to be imparted: mandatory vs recommended, how information are to be entered into the CSVs, how taxonomic information should be included, etc. It would be useful for all the necessary information to be provided in a machine-consumable way – see Sec. [4.1.4](#) for more discussion on this point.
- While the DwC-A data standard is not one that every biodiversity data infrastructure needs to support, adoption of the DwC *vocabulary* (for biodiversity data) is easier to achieve, and would greatly aid any eventual export of their data to DwC-A.
- If any new standards or vocabularies are developed, they should be mapped to existing ones.

Templates and checklists

The participants suggested that wider provision of templates to demonstrate how to format data, with clear, simple instructions and useful examples, would be useful. All stakeholders that we investigated in eDNAqua-Plan *do* have these templates. But they are (apparently) not being easily found.

⁵² <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

⁵³ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

A centralised location where one can either find all the templates, or find the pointers and explanation of the templates, was requested by several of the workshop participants. See Sec. [5.1](#) for a potential action item on this point. An example of the type of information that could be provided is given in [Table 1](#).

Participants also pointed out that there is a lack of understanding about the importance of conforming to templates, and of the consequences of not providing some information or using the recommended encoding (e.g. URI vs. string). This is because of poor understanding of FAIR data, and possibly also of the wider digital ecosystem (e.g. who uses your data and for what purpose). See Sec. [3.1](#) for more on training.

The [FAIRe](#) checklist was brought up several times during the workshop. This is a checklist of metadata necessary to make the different types of eDNA data FAIR, created by the [FAIR eDNA](#)⁵⁴ initiative (aka FAIRe), and is a resource that eDNAqua-Plan champions. While clearly useful, some participants commented that they found it quite overwhelming; the checklists are indeed quite comprehensive, as they address the different types of eDNA data separately. *If these could be “plugged into” e-notebooks, that would be a painless way for scientists to conform without having to fully understand. Sequencing platforms could also be modified to export the necessary information in the correct format, so that these would not have to be collected a-posteriori.*

The FAIRe checklist has not been formally adopted by the necessary standards organisations, and so will not help when submitting data to be published right now. *However, we understand that the initiative has the support of many of the relevant data infrastructures and we look forward to it becoming a formal part of the digital ecosystem. In particular ENA, GBIF, and GSC were part of the FAIRe initiative and along with the FAIRe lead, championed this for adoption at the GSC MixS. Lynn Schriml, the President of GSC, is keen for sample-related terms of FAIRe to be in MixS. [Ongoing efforts](#)⁵⁵ are underway to further develop and align the eDNA checklist across the GSC and TDWG standards suites.*

N.B. The MixS checklists are predominantly sample focused, whereas FAIRe has the full gamut of terms covering project, sample, sequencing, and PCR details. The enhanced (FAIRe) sequence-related metadata is being adopted into the next version of the Global Alliance [GA4GH experiments metadata](#)⁵⁶ and the intention is for all that metadata to be added to MixS.

An interesting comment from a stakeholder made after the workshop points to the need to connect with the developers of instruments and software used to make measurements/process samples. There is a rapid evolution in the type of data that can be created these days, both instrumentally and via novel software techniques.

⁵⁴ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.10.185867>

⁵⁶ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/experiments-metadata-standard/>

However, rarely is there any conversation between these developers and data technicians to allow the engineers to output data that are interoperable and are provided with instrument-relevant provenance. As a result, the data infrastructures are always playing “catch up”, slowing down any progress on standardisation, harmonisation, and publication of those new data. This is most definitely the case for eDNA.

4.1.4. Machine-interoperable data and metadata

In Sec. [3.8](#) we provide some reasons why using web standards to expose information is an enabler in moving to the future landscape. *Exposing your data formats, data models, standards, and vocabularies using web standards provides the opportunities for other data infrastructures to find the information without needing to ask first (improving efficiency), and will improve harmonisation. A data infrastructure can also choose to share all their (meta)data in this way, rather than only the potentially limited subset that fits into particular (meta)data formats that are perhaps used by some but not all: the data receiver is then the one who decides what to use, not the data sharer.*

In response to several comments about the DwC-A format made during the meeting, it was pointed out that DwC-A is a data export/sharing format, not a database format.

Not everywhere and everyone has the resources to use web technology and expose (meta)data for machine consumption. A strong statement that guidelines, templates, examples, and information sharing is important to allow those parties to engage in this modernisation, was made by several participants. See Sec. [5.1](#) for more on this topic.

N.B. Just after the workshop, the GSC MixS terms were added to the EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service: see

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/gscmixs> This will increase the ease of machine validation and interoperability with the MixS terms.

4.1.5. Data flows, from local to global; avoiding generalist repositories

The landscaping recommendation is that data flows go from local/regional/thematic to global. This is the approach taken by OBIS and GBIF and it has several advantages: distributing the effort, building in greater resilience to funding issues, ensuring multiple copies of data exist, engaging better with local communities, allowing for national differences in data security and for national sovereignty. This works well for the biodiversity data; however, for sequence data the recommendation is to use the existing global data infrastructures (INSDC: ENA in Europe, NCBI in the USA, DDBJ in Japan) which are specialised for those data and which share

(meta)data with each other as well as with other stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem. Note that there is also an effort to reach out for new INSDC partners around the globe, including the global south.

There was a short discussion on this point during the workshop. One consideration to take into account is the fact that countries differ in their approach to managing science: some prefer federation and others prefer centralisation. Where a country does not have any national data infrastructures – for example, they are not a GBIF or OBIS node – this is not an approach that will work so easily.

The data infrastructures present at this breakout session were asked how easy they found it to share their (meta)data with others. For GBIF this is a standard part of their workflow, and it helps/is necessary that GBIF's nodes and GBIF work with the same standard (DwC). In France, the national databases send their data to GBIF, but the participant added that they have to work to adapt their databases to the DNA DwC extension while still conforming to their national specifications. A few participants mentioned that there are countries with national specifications that do not necessarily match those used by trans-national data infrastructures: they then have the additional burden of updating their standards to accommodate new data types (e.g. DNA) as well as updating their mapping to that of the international data infrastructures with which they share their data. The need to map between standards is a burden that needs to be borne where data infrastructures share (meta)data; this is made harder if changes to the standards are not communicated in a timely and machine-readable manner. See Sec. [4.1.4](#) for more on this.

Sharing dataset discovery and description metadata⁵⁷ (such as found in a catalogue) is easier than data sharing, as less information and less variation in the standards and specifications is found. As such, this type of sharing should have a higher priority.

Another consideration was offered: a case where one data infrastructure became aware that their data had been harvested into another. There was no objection on principle, but rather to the fact that originating URI was not included, and some information (agent names) had been lost: the provenance chain was broken. There should be guidelines set out for how harvesting and data sharing should happen. Otherwise this could become a blocker to uptake of this recommendation.

Dealing with duplication of data was briefly discussed; this can be an issue when data are shared across data infrastructures. Different data infrastructures deal with this in different ways, identifying and flagging data that are or could be duplicates. One way to deal with the duplication is to use the accreditations to the observations to the submitters ORCID: GBIF is working on this. One could also ensure links between (duplicated) data are always included. There is already a working mechanism to accredit your ORCID to any data object in ENA. Furthermore, many

⁵⁷ i.e. metadata that allows data to be found via any search interface, and that describes the temporal, spatial, parameter, and taxonomic coverage, and the background of the data.

infrastructures such as GBIF and INSDC have associated literature references, although in practice this is incomplete as users do not often avail themselves of the service. Literature cross-references to projects are automatically provided by [ePubMedCentral](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/)⁵⁸ for ENA data. Another issue arising from data duplication is where one record receives corrections but the other(s) does not: conveying information about corrections in an automated way is possible, but requires both the provider and receiver to process that information.

One of the eDNAqua-Plan landscaping recommendations is to avoid publishing specialist data in generalist repositories: generalist repositories generally do not include sufficient specialised metadata or vocabularies to allow for good data searches, and while they can accommodate a wide range of data formats, they are unlikely to have templates for all the possible data types or the tools to quality check those data before being published. In addition, people will generally find a specialist dataset in a specialist repository, where they expect such data to be. Generalist repositories are often provided by journals, and while laudable (as it encourages data sharing), we believe that these should focus on the data contained immediately within the papers published in the journals, rather than source data such as the sequences and ASV tables or entire reference libraries. In addition, we believe that data should be findable as data *from data repositories* rather than from the starting point of a scientific article (which may or may not be open access). Several of the participants had not encountered this reasoning before, and they responded positively to the suggestion.

4.1.6. eDNA data in biodiversity archives

The participants were asked their opinion on the question of helping users of biodiversity data who do not fully understand the science and practice of DNA analysis: how can they interpret the data correctly so they can use them knowingly? It was felt that biodiversity databases should not take on the role of data interpretation and analysis, otherwise they might risk data integrity and trustability: how to interpret data is always a complex issue. *However*, the database should provide the critical metadata that is needed to make the necessary interpretations (e.g. the sampling methods used, the reference libraries used, etc). The most important thing is to make DNA-based observations clearly distinguishable and easy to filter from traditional species observations (preferably easier than currently in GBIF).

4.1.7 Interoperable and open bioinformatics outputs

With respect to the suggestion that more bioinformatics outputs, other than just the taxonomic table and the DNA sequence, should be regularly published as they are the proof of the results (provenance): the consensus was that this should be of a low

⁵⁸ <https://europepmc.org>

priority, especially compared to everything else that “we would like to have improved in the digital ecosystem”. This was because bioinformatics outputs are often very large and numerous, and no data infrastructure at present will archive all that material. Many of the outputs can only be interpreted by experts, and the consensus was that experts “will reprocess the data anyway”. Finally, it was believed that “this will never happen” (*although it may be that we are still at the stage of collating data together and there are not many re-use cases yet*). In post-workshop comments, the point was raised that raw OTU tables (including control samples, any ASV that were removed for various reasons like potential contamination, out-of-scope taxa etc.) should always be published; QC steps that differ between projects will alter the final tables produced, and so these raw tables are important provenance data. If one only publishes the curated OTU table and raw data, then eDNA datasets really should have sample metadata that contain control sample information.

What was considered more feasible and desirable is to mandate that all bioinformatics codes/workflows are published, with a templated metadata description of the code (e.g. as provided by [CodeMeta](#)⁵⁹), and that the inputs to any running of the code were also provided along with the results. Some of this metadata is already requested by omics and biodiversity data infrastructures, although they are generally not mandatory and not required to be accessible (e.g. it is necessary to only give the name of the code rather than the URI/DOI). *Additionally, sample metadata that documents control information (e.g., control IDs, purpose, and links between control and environmental sample IDs) is essential for re-analysis. When raw sequence data, analytical code, and such metadata are all available, the shared data become fully reproducible and re-analysable. Currently the details about controls are not requested by data infrastructures (e.g., GBIF) hence missing from the majority of published eDNA data.*

Another recommendation was that reproducible workflows are published, and making workflows available on open access cloud environments so that those with the knowledge, but not the resources, can run them. Is this something to be provided, in Europe, via EOSC?

There is a common problem regarding bioinformatics codes developed as part of PhD work or within time-limited projects: too often these become stale as the developer moves on to a new job. Where developers do try to maintain their codes, they often have to do that in their own time: this is not sustainable, fair, or FAIR. *The organisations (universities) under which such work is done should be encouraged to ensure findability, long-term access, and perhaps even continued development (e.g. to update as external data used in the code are also updated), and to fund that themselves. At a minimum they should require that those codes are FAIR and well documented (in open access locations) before the developer moves on.*

⁵⁹ <https://codemeta.github.io/>

A current gap in the eDNA digital ecosystem is the publication of ASVs as (meta)data. *There are some places these objects can be published: the ASV sequence is a mandatory or highly recommended requirement when publishing DNA results in GBIF and OBIS; ENA is currently developing a submission service for OTU and ASV objects and accompanying metadata as annotations (expected Q1 2026); and they can also be submitted to the [Swedish ASV portal](#)⁶⁰ (which is linked to GBIF). Scientists should be encouraged (especially by the journals) to ensure that their ASVs are also published, not only their sequences.*

4.2. Reference libraries and bioinformatics

Comprehensive and good quality reference libraries are a key cog in the landscape, as these provide the fundamental information to enable taxonomic identification by sequences. In this context, bioinformatic workflows are defined as those which structure the reference library information and the systematic computational selection and processing of eDNA sequences to then subsequently make the taxonomic identification.

The stakeholders included in the two breakout B sessions on day 2 were those involved in creating and maintaining reference libraries, those working in bioinformatics, and those concerned with including taxonomic information within omics and biodiversity datasets. The [discussion topics](#)⁶¹ focussed on the recommendations from the landscaping report made for these stakeholders, with a particular focus on essential metadata for their digital objects, interoperable data formats, curation principles, and on the feasibility, bottlenecks, and enablers of the recommendations. Here we have collated and categorised the questions and breakout discussions during the workshop.

The stated consensus in eDNAqua-Plan is to have a diverse portfolio of independent reference libraries, each with their own focus. Crucially however, the metadata should be interoperable between each other, with a federated metadata search engine running across them all so that users/machines can find the appropriate data sources.

4.2.1. Reference libraries: metadata curation and completeness

General Points about Reference Library Metadata

Participants indicated that they would like to know what metadata eDNAqua-Plan thinks are needed, and the recommended syntax to use, for reference libraries (more

⁶⁰ <https://asv-portal.biodiversitydata.se/>

⁶¹

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bjjZgFHgStKw8ol8tsbjbislmhj8oecB8F56hkg_8/edit?usp=sharing

for the contents of the library, than for the library as a digital object). It was clear that by “metadata” for the references we were talking about information on discoverability, scope, usability (provenance), the accompanying taxonomic information, and any geographic, temporal, environmental etc. values. They also wanted to discuss where reference library (meta)data should be published, as this was not clear to all. These points are addressed in this section and also elsewhere in Sec. [4.2](#).

Curation and completeness

A key objective of taxonomic curation is to homogenise taxonomic names for a given phylogenetic clade (or for identical / near-identical sequences).

Reference databases require much human curation. There was a discussion on standardising the way to create a database using software (including AI), instead of cataloguing all databases and trying to make them interoperable. [CRABS](#)^{R3} (Creating Reference databases for Amplicon-Based Sequencing), is a pipeline for automatically creating a curated reference database for a designed sequence region. This does not work in all cases, in particular for species for which there is not much sequence data available, but could provide a good solution otherwise. It was pointed out that using AI to overwrite manual curation may not provide good results, but AI could be used for identifying, and perhaps fixing inconsistencies in existing reference libraries. Another idea was to crowdsource the taxonomic curation, with a defined template and metadata to keep it consistent. It was also felt to be important to use existing tools, before creating new ones.

Incomplete reference libraries can be a very limiting problem for practical employment of eDNA for biomonitoring (this was a particular experience in Brazil). Hence, complete reference libraries, as well as providing up-to-date information on completeness, is important for eDNA to be taken up in national monitoring programmes. A similar comment is recorded in Sec. [4.2.4](#).

The WP2 analysis showed that people download NCBI and BOLD data to create their own reference libraries to use in their own bioinformatics workflows. To ensure that those workflows always produce up-to-date results from these reference libraries, it is necessary that the authors of those workflows (1) can find a list of the reference data they import via URIs (ensuring reproducibility), and (2) can easily find any changes that have been made to the information associated with those references, i.e. warnings on updates, changes, additions by the data infrastructures are issued promptly and ideally using web-tech rather than only via a (human-readable) web page.

BOLD has an impressive infrastructure for reference libraries: e.g. the [GEANS1 library](#)⁶². BOLD’s focus is on animals and the CO1 barcode, and also some plants (rbcL and matK); they have less coverage of microorganisms and fungi etc. INSDC

⁶² <https://portal.boldsystems.org/recordset/DS-GEANS1>

(NCBI, ENA, DDBJ) has a wider coverage, but is less well curated than BOLD. Much QC is needed for both BOLD and INSDC downloads.

Reference Sequences

Ideally, one should always publish new reference sequences in a public database. It was stated that the uploading of sequences to be used as references is not easy at ENA for people without experience. This is a bottleneck to the community getting the information into curated reference libraries.

There was a debate on what to do with the curated versions of reference sequences, and how to share the curations with the community, but we did not come to a consensus on a best way to share: different approaches are taken for different reasons. INSDC will not accept third party curations to the archive copies, although corrective curations to INSDC records can be done using the [ENA Clearinghouse](#)⁶³. The French National reference database is considering hosting a local copy of the relevant INSDC “reference” sequences that they use, as well as linking to the INSDC records. This would increase sustainability and allow curation of these reference sequences, but is also duplication (=cost).

A question was asked whether scientists should also publish their collections of sequences taken from public repositories (e.g. NCBI) and used as a reference library. The eDNAqua-Plan answer is “yes”: these curated or tailored libraries provide the provenance of the sequence assignment results. However, it is not necessarily the case that the new library *itself* needs to be published, instead the methodology (e.g. as code) used to collate the sequences and the sequence identifiers would be sufficient, as long as the provided information allowed for a complete re-creation of that reference library, and that the source sequences are open access.

Regarding the construction of reference databases, one should take on board that different domains have different standard practices: in insect identification, for example, it is important to have several individuals of the same species.

There is a need for a metric of completeness of reference databases, to show where the data gaps are. This has been done in particular PhD projects that some participants were aware of, but the information is not systematically retained.

A further point was made about using radically different taxonomic classifiers. Where phylogenetic placement is used instead of plain best-alignment identifications for example, their reference libraries may need to be formatted differently.

⁶³ https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/annotation/clearinghouse_for_ENA_users.html

4.2.2. Reference libraries: national reference libraries

There are initiatives in Europe to have national reference libraries (France and The Netherlands were mentioned). These will typically not store the sequences themselves, but have links to the relevant data. Reasons for this include: nations want databases that reflect their own national strategy on biodiversity, it allows for more efficient monitoring and documenting of their own biodiversity and can plug gaps in larger databases such as BOLD and ENA, and it allows for (some degree of) sovereignty over their information. In addition, it allows for information to be provided in the local language(s) rather than solely in English. However, not all nations have the capacity to do this, and that is where the larger data infrastructures and projects, such as iBOL, play a role.

We discussed how smaller reference libraries, such as (some of) those in France, have some advantages over larger/global ones: for example, their expert curators tend to be more engaged, they have a greater flexibility over the taxonomic backbones used, and they can align with local eDNA monitoring programmes – using their own reference libraries but filling in any gaps from other ones. (This latter only works if everyone shares their own reference libraries.)

A suggestion was made to reach out to those resources to discover what works and their idiosyncrasies. The French national system, for example, plans to have links to the major relevant public data infrastructures and for it to be an open portal for data sharing. If all national reference databases “signed up” to the same set of (meta)data and data sharing standards, that would greatly improve the smoothness of this part of the digital landscape.

Note that the French National Reference Library metadata field names are a combination of existing metadata standards, in particular BOLD’s BCDM and TDWG’s Darwin Core (DwC) terms. (As part of the BGE WP8, there is a mapping for BOLD’s BCDM and GSC MIxS and other ENA terms – see the [BOLD](#)⁶⁴ and the [BGE](#)⁶⁵ GitHub resources).

There was discussion around the differences between the eDNAqua-Plan vision and that of BOLD, and questions on what effect this will have and how? *This was answered after the workshop:*

The eDNAqua-Plan vision is to have specialist, well-curated reference libraries with a shared, standard, federated data model. BOLD is a less curated, more comprehensive and centralised reference library. There is a difference in vision, however: BOLD has notably become more open with sharing metadata, allowing computational bridges to be made, and their barcode data model has been in GitHub since 2023. During 2025, BOLD and ENA worked together and now share cross-references, with continued metadata and barcode sequence feeds to both NCBI or also to ENA (without duplication). The feed to ENA is planned to have richer

⁶⁴ <https://github.com/DNAdiversity/BCDM>

⁶⁵ <https://github.com/bge-barcoding/StayingMapped/tree/main/sssom-mapping>

metadata and thus help more easily integrate BOLD with the rest of the data ecosystem, as many reference libraries pull at least some data from INSDC databases and GBIF are actively planning to integrate more metadata from environmentally relevant ENA.

4.2.3. Reference libraries: essential metadata

The BOLD list of metadata is very extensive (see for example their [documented templates](#)⁶⁶). The eDNAqua-Plan approach is to not repeat this, but to recommend a set of **essential/minimum** requirements for absolutely obligatory metadata to be provided with all data and which should be directly accessible (to humans and machines) from the specimen/sequence identifier (see [Table 2](#)). As already mentioned in Sec. [3.6](#), a common feedback from the data infrastructures, and also data submitters, is that having a (too) high bar for metadata discourages data submission. It was pointed out that having a good set of essential metadata would allow for an evaluation of the taxonomic identification and hence the quality of the reference. However, eDNAqua-Plan believes that the evaluation of the quality of the reference sequence, including the certainty of the taxonomic name, should be provided by the (curated) reference library. Providing this quality assessment of the reference sequence would allow for only a minimal set of essential metadata. If the specimen identifier is provided, then all the specimen-metadata, such as images, vouchers etc., can be accessed from the original collection. Having the essential metadata would also allow a ranking to be done.

Some very useful, but not essential, metadata are the habitat/environmental types, but the terminology used over these data infrastructures needs more harmonisation (e.g. including land cover types and climatic regions [albeit these are less relevant to our aquatic domain]). It is also important that these terminologies (vocabularies) should be used correctly: for example, as pointed out in Sec. [4.1.3](#), when using ENVO terms they should be given as URIs rather than strings.

The relative importance of institute and contact details for those that curate/validate the reference library entries was considered: this is helpful in the short term, but less in the longer term as people move jobs or retire. *IDs – ORCID, ROR, etc – are better to use, as long as they remember to open access to their contact information and make prompt updates.*

Sampling and ABS permits inherited in the reference library from their physical specimens is also important metadata. This field is already in the BOLD metadata list, and is compulsory for reference genome databases (e.g. GoAT).

Clear versioning of reference libraries was also flagged as useful.

⁶⁶ <https://boldsystems.org/resource-hub/templates/>

Having the reference library metadata managed globally by a standards body such as GSC was proposed.

There was a general consensus that following the relevant FAIR terms for the reference sequence set should be done. It was noted that among the FAIR terms, the confidence on the reference sequence (not the taxonomic assignment) is missing.

Metadata Formats

Darwin Core archive format implemented in GBIF seems to be very efficient for sending data packages around; to which should be added some additional fields from the FAIR checklists.

4.2.4. Reference libraries: sequence curation

There were some differing opinions regarding the curation of reference libraries: some felt that users need well-curated libraries and others felt that there are varying levels of curation possible, depending on the needs of the user, and so it is best to leave it to the user to decide what to do. One can include environmental sequences as reference sequences for micro-organisms e.g. diatoms, but cannot for larger organisms⁶⁷. It was noted that there are some large, metadata-rich reference libraries and others that are (instead) well curated: users have differing use cases, so both approaches are useful. An example for the usefulness of comprehensive reference libraries but which may be less well-curated is for DNA monitoring: if you just want to know if a species has been seen before in a particular location it is vital to have a comprehensive reference library to match against. As we would like to encourage the uptake of (e)DNA among monitoring efforts, this should be considered an important use-case.

There were very different expectations for the reporting and construction of confidence levels on the taxonomic identification between organism groups. Reporting confidence levels alone is not enough, as different tools provide different results and work with different algorithms and assumptions; also reporting the *type* of confidence value (i.e. sequence similarity, query coverage, bootstrap confidence) is necessary. *FAIR has the field tax_assign_cat (sequence similarity – usually BLAST; sequence composition – usually RDP or other bootstrap-based analysis; other), which gets a step closer to clarifying the quality type.* In addition, not all tools provide confidence levels.

⁶⁷ As microorganisms cannot be isolated, cultured or described morphologically, it is acceptable that an environmental DNA sequence alone represents a species. Multicellular organisms must be tied to a physical specimen that shows details a sequence cannot (anatomy, developmental stage, etc). Microbial genomes are also smaller than for multicellular, and hence it is easier for metagenomics to construct an entire species.

Should we consider the need to incorporate new, better standardised metadata terms to cover the “quality” of the identification? It was pointed out that even if you have good metadata, an expert curator should still review the data. There was concern, however, in being able to obtain sufficient expert curators: perhaps some level of automated curation should be investigated. This need not necessarily be AI-aided, but in any case to develop the AI training models requires good metadata *now*. Good ideas mooted were to: generate a reference library “good practice curation guide”, and to build a community of curators tagged with their expertise domain.

A consistent recommendation was to link to *local* taxonomic experts to curate/update species lists, occurrences and nomenclature. This uplifts the value and the role of taxonomists in this context. It was suggested to reward taxonomic experts to get them onboard, but we had no idea of what sort of reward system to use (however, some of the enablers discussed in Sec. [3.9](#) could apply here). In some communities e.g. in Germany, reference sequences coming from a whitelist of experts are updated.

During the workshop there was a request for recommendations on tools and methods to do taxonomic curation aimed at reference libraries. There are two main steps, which are both necessary to produce trustable results:

- Step 1 - check the sequence quality:
 - E.g. poor quality can be homopolymer and undetermined nucleotides.
 - Evaluate the number of undetermined nucleotides (“N”), homopolymers reverse-complement sequences, introns, deletions.
 - For SSU/LSU: HMMs profiles can be checked as well as the secondary structure.
- Step 2 - check synonyms and phylogeny. These are some methods to help the taxonomic expert to curate the taxonomic names, together with the metadata available with the sequence.
 1. **Expert curation based on phylogenies.** If neighbouring sequences have non-homogeneous names, check for
 1. scientific publications
 2. synonyms in taxonomic databases - may have to change some old synonyms
 3. check if there is an identification mistake, e.g. to go back to the voucher metadata
 2. **Expert curation based on clustering genetically similar sequences.** Check non-homogeneous names following a defined protocol.
 3. **Expert curation based on self assignment** again following a defined protocol.
 4. **Automated curation procedures based on bioinformatics or AI.** Semi-automated to fully automated as developments progress, with human intervention for clarifying intricacies at low taxonomic levels. e.g. Diat.barcode, UNITE, Barcode, Audit & Grade System (BAGS), BGE library curation tool.

It was stated that the principles are more important than the actual tools used. All tools can be used for data curation and the discussion group was open to other better tools in a decade or more.

In the opinion of the experts, it is the intersection between metadata, curation procedure, and interoperability that makes the reference library useful and trustable. It helps to have a large team of curators e.g. 10-15 are used by DIATOMS.

One could look at the technology readiness levels (TRL) framework as a guide for reference sequence curation levels, where the “readiness” reflects: whether the sequence has a specimen, if it has been closely matched to other sequences with reference specimens. etc.

Mapping taxonomies

There was discussion about mapping different taxonomies to each other. This is a recommendation of the landscaping report and the workshop participants agreed with this: it increases the usability and interoperability of the information, and widens the audience of users who will be able to fully understand the taxonomic designations and integrate them with their data/research.

There is no single high-coverage and scientifically-accurate taxonomy, although there are relative specialist ones e.g. AlgaeBase and WoRMS and generalist ones e.g. NCBI taxonomy. See Sec. 4.4 for a short additional discussion on taxonomy backbones. In the French reference library (National Inventory of Natural Heritage) they have a taxonomy checklist (called [TaxRef](#)⁶⁸) that uses WoRMS, and also includes the publication of every species found in France.

Taxonomic mistakes in existing repositories

It was noted that some sequences in the INSDC repositories have the wrong species identification – this is an inevitable part of science, but the issue is that participants found it hard to get these corrected (see also Sec. 4.1.1 about faster correcting of metadata). Participants suggested having extra fields/tags to tag the misidentifications and to provide the likely correct taxonomic identification in INSDC records, or to encourage the use of tools such as the [ENA Clearinghouse](#)⁶⁹, that allows third party annotation on any ENA object.

If reference database (meta)data and taxonomies are shared: can taxonomic annotations be routinely checked between different databases? This could be a way for finding and reducing errors.

⁶⁸ <https://www.data.gouv.fr/datasets/referentiel-taxonomique-taxref/>, <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0e61f8fe-7d25-4f81-ada7-d970bbb2c6d6>

⁶⁹ https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/annotation/clearinghouse_for_ENA_users.html

4.2.5. Reference libraries: GBIF prototyping of a service/portal

There were some concerns voiced on the plans of GBIF to start prototyping a reference library service/portal. Other data infrastructures, such as ENA or BOLD, are already in this space, and would be a more logical host of such a service; a new GBIF development may add confusion.

However, given that GBIF has these plans, perhaps this prototype could be in collaboration with BOLD or ENA (or similar data infrastructures). From GBIF's side, the intention is to do this work with everyone interested (we note that after the meeting, eDNAqua-Plan attended a GBIF workshop on this reference library prototype and presented our recommendations). It is a large undertaking, in particular to do it in a way that is interoperable with other data infrastructures, data providers, data users. In addition, as GBIF have (automatically) harvested all ENA and BOLD records, and especially if those other data infrastructures have no similar plans, then this action will ultimately be beneficial to the digital ecosystem. Interoperability, findability, and reusability (provenance) will be key to its uptake and sustainable usefulness, as well as ensuring metadata are provided to allow people to find and track the data as it propagates through the portal.

4.2.6. Bioinformatics: ASV and OTU Tables

The reporting of ASV or OTU tables was considered to be very useful, as they are dataset-specific and thus not directly interchangeable.

It is important that bioinformatic steps are properly documented. See also Sec. [4.1.7](#).

4.2.7. Bioinformatics: Primers

As reported in Sec. [4.1.1](#), reporting on the primers used should be part of the metadata (and/or part of the dataset published). The choice of primers determines the specificity of detections for taxonomic groups, and is thus essential to consider in data re-use. Additionally, generating in-silico PCR outputs about primers specificity and coverage could be a quite standard way to be aware about potential biases (e.g. ecoPrimers^{R4} is a very good tool).

One suggestion was to create and maintain a unifying platform which can suggest primers for specific taxonomic groups/purposes, protocols, repositories (see also Sec. [4.1.7](#)). If this can be maintained sustainably, it could become a standard reference and result in greater uniformisation of primer methodology. As reported in Sec. [4.1.1](#), MGnify's [PIMENTO](#)^{R5} tool could be a starting point for this.

4.2.8. Bioinformatics: Improvements in metadata and standards

During the discussions, one participant stated that some of the bioinformatics intermediate outputs (results) and the code "...does not have a proper home. Raw reads go to ENA, and curated OTU tables and final taxonomic assignment of each curated OTU go to OBIS and GBIF. But in between, there is not really a place for the intermediate data and the bioinformatics code. The information about what you did, quality checking, manual clean ups and other manual activities, where do you put it? Big databases don't want these datasets."

There was a general agreement that publishing the code/workflows should be a priority. GitHub+Zenodo, combined with templates such as provided by CodeMeta, were mentioned as a way to publish code and standardised code metadata and obtain a DOI. This same approach can also be used to share the results of running the code on any particular dataset, providing the provenance of that execution and where desired, more of the intermediate results: Zenodo and other generalist repositories can play a role here.

In the case of bioinformatics, the size and quantity of the outputs (in particular all the intermediate outputs) is a bottleneck to their publication, but additionally there is no strong movement towards sharing these data in the first place. See also Sec. 4.1.7, where it was concluded that this should be considered a low priority. However, it was considered important for bioinformatics code to be FAIR, and that publishers of code/code papers should require that code is published with standardised metadata descriptions.

There is a general lack of both standards and adherence to existing standards when it comes to bioinformatics outputs: which metadata should be mandatory, how these should be reported, the structuring and formatting of the significant bioinformatics outputs, the semantic annotations (vocabularies, ontologies) to use, metadata descriptions for the bioinformatics codes, etc. *There are in fact, already guidelines for making software FAIR (SoFAIR⁷⁰, FAIR-Impact⁷¹, FAIR-EASE^{R6}, CodeMeta⁷² to name just a few projects and their resources).* Specific guidelines for the formatting and/or describing of the outputs (for humans and machines to read and understand) should be created: semantically annotated (interoperable) taxonomic outputs, ASV reporting, etc would make it much easier to then publish those results in all the different relevant data infrastructures (taxonomic results in biodiversity archives, ASVs in ASV archives, etc). There is a need for better checklists for publishing bioinformatics results, so that the provenance information is properly provided. All of these should come from the community but leadership is required to make it happen: a suggestion

⁷⁰ <https://sofair.org/>

⁷¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/metrics-software>

⁷² <https://codemeta.github.io/>

was to have EU-level working groups. Some of the community are creating a [BeBOP template](#)⁷³ for this (along with the FAIRe community).

The question of where best to store workflows etc. was discussed. It was agreed that a single recommendation, and a recommendation to store in a single place, should be avoided as having redundancy of workflow archiving is important.

With respect to the DNA extension to DwC: it was pointed out that the DwC vocabulary does not cover all the fields that would be needed to describe an eDNA bioinformatics workflow, and adoption of the extra terms from the FAIRe checklist would be important. It was apparent from the discussion that people know the principles of DwC, DwC DNA-Derived Data extension and MIxS, but not all their details.

Bioinformatics code should always be published: its metadata records, its metadata description (e.g CodeMeta, FAIRe checklist).

1. There should be a formalised, machine-readable metadata descriptions of code (e.g. CodeMeta, FAIRe)
2. All bioinformatics codes should be FAIR – there are profiles for software to make them FAIR
3. Output data should be FAIR

4.2.9. What does a successful future for reference libraries look like?

Success means: all taxonomic assignments of eDNA data are done using quality-controlled, taxonomically-curated and thus reliable reference databases. The vision of how to achieve that was outlined. In response participants emphasised that federating existing reference-database efforts and resources is both feasible and highly desirable. Such coordination would encourage the adoption of shared standards and strengthen capacity building. Participants also highlighted the importance of supporting established taxonomic backbones, e.g. AlgaeBase. They noted the need for precise wording: what is being developed is fundamentally a DNA reference library, which may later be used for eDNA, but is not an eDNA-specific library in itself.

Bottlenecks and Enablers in Implementing this

Several challenges were identified. In many countries, establishing national or regional reference-database portals is difficult due to limited funding and technical capacity. Moreover, sequence-data sovereignty is not always a priority for governments or institutions.

A key enabler will be engaging the taxonomic community, particularly experts from southeastern Europe. This requires designing meaningful incentive systems and

⁷³ https://github.com/BeBOP-OBON/0_protocol_collection_template

reinforcing the value of classical taxonomy. Mobilising community taxonomists – such as contributors to iNaturalist – could also be highly beneficial. Participants suggested creating virtual networks or organising hackathons dedicated to reference-data curation.

National initiatives must also be considered. Countries such as France, the Netherlands, and Germany are developing databases under their own national sovereignty. Collaboration with these efforts is essential to ensure compatibility. These initiatives – at least in the case of France – ultimately share the same goals: to use existing data while also making their own data openly accessible.

What is needed now is agreement on common practices, including shared standards and web services, to bring these efforts together.

How can we make it possible?

Propose a set of metadata broken down into essential, highly recommend and recommend metadata. Open a period of consultation with all reference databases (big and small) and national initiatives, and get it then ratified under a standards body.

It is also important to obtain long-term funding for core reference databases – there is currently no core funding for maintaining them.

Which organisation or entity would be best positioned to establish and maintain a federated, high-quality DNA reference library?

When considering which organisation or entity would be best positioned to establish and maintain a federated, high-quality DNA reference library, several candidates emerged from the discussion.

The **Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN)** was highlighted as a strong contender due to its established infrastructure, long-standing experience in managing genomic resources, and direct connections to taxonomic experts. Its existing global coordination mechanisms could provide a solid foundation for a sustained reference-database effort.

CETAF (Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities) was also identified as a suitable organisation. CETAF's network of museums, herbaria, and taxonomic institutions aligns closely with the need for scientifically curated reference data, and it naturally connects to capacity-building and standard-setting efforts – tying into previous discussions on governance and harmonisation.

iBOL Europe represents another relevant initiative, particularly because of its focus on DNA barcoding and its established ties with European biodiversity infrastructures. Its experience in mobilising communities and developing standards could support the broader federated model.

Participants also noted the importance of ensuring that **microbial diversity** is adequately represented. This raises the question of whether dedicated microbial reference-database communities or infrastructures should be integrated as partners or represented through a specialised coordinating body. The fact that microbial databasing networks are already well established – and strongly linked to expert taxonomists – suggests that they could be incorporated efficiently into a broader federation.

Overall, the consensus leaned toward a model that builds on existing, trusted infrastructures – potentially through a coordinated effort involving GGBN, CETAF, and iBOL Europe – while ensuring that microbial expertise is explicitly included from the outset.

4.3. Biobanks and culture collections

Topics concerning data and data systems in biobanks, culture collections, or information related to taxonomic systems and concepts were discussed in two sessions (Breakout C).

The landscaping recommendations (see the [session input document](#)⁷⁴) to improve data input, storage and exchange for biobanks and culture collections were the main focus of the discussions in these sessions.

The first session started with an explanation of what biobanks and culture collections are and their activities relevant in the context of this workshop:

- Culture collections for micro-organisms. Most of the strains are alive and cryo-preserved and are used by industry. They follow standards that allow their customers to use the catalogue and find the cultures they require. An example is the DSMZ (Germany) and there exist similar culture collections in Spain and in the USA.
- Natural history museums. They also have standards and codes (e.g. Latimer Core) for the specimens or samples that they have in their collection, how it was collected, and the preservation procedures.
- Living sample collections, for example spore collection of botanic gardens, etc.
- Collections that store frozen DNA extracts. Where they then sequence those, the data are added to omics databases (e.g. NCBI) and the accession codes linked the (remaining) frozen samples.

⁷⁴

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bjiZgFHgStKw8ol8tsbjbislmhj8oecB8F56hlkg_8/edit?usp=sharing

4.3.1. Heterogeneity

Heterogeneity in size, sample type and taxonomic scope is a strength but also a challenge for integration of data standards and data systems: how can we handle heterogeneity of samples within biobanks and how can we increase interoperability across different specialised biobanks?

Biobanks and culture collections in Europe have a broad coverage in terms of taxonomy, sample types, sample preservation and storage methods, and management architectures. The diversity of culture collections and biobanks also extends to their mode of operation: some will have a national/regional mandate, others will operate only within their own organisations, yet others will provide a service to external agents (commercially or not).

Collections are created and used by people with very different backgrounds. It needs to be borne in mind that the users of culture collections and biobanks are not only researchers, but also industry. These audiences have different use-cases for interacting with, and wanting information from, the collections; and where they also deposit material in the collections, they will have different expectations of the amount of metadata that they will provide with that material.

Different taxonomic backbones are in use for different types of organisms. In addition, taxonomic levels are not harmonised and taxonomic diversity at the species level or lower (molecular unit or strain) may not be adequately reflected by the nomenclatural system in use, or the nomenclatural system may not be standardised.

These factors are not only a challenge for the biobanks and culture collections at an individual level, but also hinder coordination, harmonisation, and standardisation across institutions. This complicates the consideration of the recommendations to make to harmonise and standardise the metadata they retain and share regarding their materials. Consider also that smaller organisations (in size, in scope, or in operations) will have different resources and different priorities than the larger ones.

4.3.2. Digital access and metadata

What steps can we take towards adopting common metadata standards and schemas? Digital access is improving, but it has not yet reached many of the biobanks and especially the smaller ones still struggle to improve access to their sample metadata and related information via the internet for everyone. One of the big issues is the lack of widely known and accepted metadata standards.

In analogy of the problems faced when trying to connect the data across different biobanks the [WISE](http://wise.europe.eu)⁷⁵ data portal was mentioned as an example of connecting

⁷⁵ <http://wise.europe.eu>

different databases across various countries. However, making these connections is made much more difficult by the fact that there are different ways of expressing the same variable, i.e. that this database is not really interoperable.

[GGBN](https://www.ggbn.org/ggbn_portal/)⁷⁶ and its data portal was pointed to as an example of working towards a solution for interoperability. It has a data standard that is part of the Darwin Core standard. We note here that TDWG maintains or links to other standards that apply to biological material and collections: e.g. Access to Biological Collection Data (ABCD) and Latimer Core (LrC). It was suggested that these should form the metadata foundation for all biobanks and culture collections.

It is also important to make recommendations on the syntax to use *in* the metadata, for example an aliquot material type, etc: the terminology of information also needs to be standardised.

One very important metadatum for any sample (/strain) is its ID. First of all, the ID should be unique and persistent. Thorough ID management is needed because collections can consist of material that come from all over the place, that are sent to all over the place, and can go back many years (decades, centuries). ID systems should allow for full track and trace of material and its metadata, should be sustainable to collection (and metadata) growth, moreover it should be mandatory that the IDs are assigned to the metadata of any subsequent material or data derived from that material, in a named field that should be included in the metadata models of all data infrastructures that deal with DNA data or DNA-derived data. Most organisations create IDs that are unique to themselves and only accessible from within their own collection – i.e. a persistent identifier (PID) that means little unless you know from where it comes. With the eDNA digital ecosystem being so global and producing different types of data that are archived in different types of repositories, it is strongly recommended that all of these IDs are also uniform resource identifiers (URIs), i.e. online accessible. In the same breath, all the metadata that is associated with those IDs need also to be online accessible and open access. Note that ID management for collections can be quite complex – where sub-sets (and sub-sub-sets etc) and derivations of material are frequently made. It is very likely that there are organisations and regions that will be very reluctant to move to such a system, partly due to an inertia to change, partly due to a lack of expertise. Many organisations will need guidance in implementing this (see also Sec. [5.1](#)). *NB it is not necessary that an ID carries information within itself (i.e. you do not need to append sub-setting codes to the ID of the parent material), better, in fact, are IDs that are random strings, and the links between the IDs are made in an ID-database.*

One participant pointed out that where metadata already exists for a sample (e.g. some morphological description and a DNA sequence), this information needs to be

⁷⁶ https://www.ggbn.org/ggbn_portal/

semantically annotated and properly interlinked – otherwise you could have different identifiers for information derived from a single sample. See Sec. [3.8](#) for a suggestion to use AI for this.

Having physical samples is very important regarding the linking of classical and molecular based taxonomy, especially for historical and later revised applications of taxonomic names. We need to avoid the loss of historical information, therefore we need to focus on linking the information. This can be done using linked open data (LOD), however this is not straightforward to people managing biobanks (very often still done in spreadsheets or on paper). There is a need for user interfaces that are intuitive to use as well as training in the fundamental principles of data science for practitioners.

An interesting issue regarding traceability via metadata was raised: material taken from collections undergo different steps of subsequent processing, producing different material and/or data as a result. The metadata standard for the original and new material and the data may not be the same. For example: samples for preserved biological specimens have various metadata standards, ISO standards; take a sample from the specimen for DNA and those samples and the subsequent digital DNA will have other standards. Anyone who wishes to trace one endpoint to another will have to deal with these different, unconnected, standards – a potential barrier to understanding and provenance. *Crosswalks between the ontologies underpinning the standards (i.e. mapping them to each other) could be considered, over the entire digital landscape.*

Biobanks and culture collections hold many different types of samples from many different ecosystems which are used for many different purposes. These institutions therefore need to accommodate different, field-specific data standards for their data systems, which should ideally be designed in a hierarchical way with no overlap. Such a requirement greatly adds to the complexity of any data models or ontologies that are to be adopted or mapped to. This is not an impossible hurdle and there are ways to manage it (maintaining or mapping to different standards for different parts of their collections, for example). However, it does necessitate coordination among the different biobanks and culture collections as this issue should be addressed collectively rather than implementing a new mix of data standards at each institution individually.

As with other data infrastructures, biobanks and culture collection will have to deal with “historical” material and associated metadata. In this case, in fact, “historical” can mean from a hundred years ago. Metadata may still be hand-written on cards that need to be interpreted and digitised (i.e. photographed and transcribed), and the specificity of some of those metadata (e.g. locations) will be much lower than required in our modern times; additionally, as geographic names change with time, some location names may no longer exist. People mandated with the interpretation of

historical data and metadata need to be familiar with the context (history, geography, research practices, linguistics etc.) of the sample collection to avoid the introduction of errors in this process. These added burdens will need to be acknowledged in all eDNAqua-Plan recommendations issued to these organisations. *Perhaps there is something to learn from those who manage historical document collections? One main difference with historical documents is that they usually contain their own context (written into the document), while for items in natural history collections the context often has to come from external sources (e.g. associated documentation). Such context can be difficult to transcribe into spreadsheets, and guidance on creating knowledge graphs that can accommodate interpretations of these (meta)data as well as to document the process of reaching these interpretations, is required.*

During both sessions, many discussions pointed out that a heterogeneity of processing and handling of material in biobanks and culture collections takes place. Standardised metadata will need to be able to accommodate sufficient descriptions that provenance is fully provided for all samples in a collection.

4.3.3. Genetic (meta)data

Integration of genetic and bioinformatic data: the integration of these data is uneven at present, with an heterogeneous use of DNA-specific terms across vocabularies relevant for biobanks and culture collections (DNA source, handling, storage methods, etc). How can we move towards a stronger model of traceability from sample to published data? How can we improve integration with external bioinformatic resources? Interoperable metadata, and *crosswalks between the ontologies* as suggested in the previous section, would help, but this is something that requires considerable resources to put into place.

4.3.4. Legal compliance and traceability

Nagoya Protocol, ABS, and BBNJ: are all requirements set by international treaties related to the collection and utilisation of genetic material and potentially derived data. What best practices exist for dealing with the requirements set by these various international treaties? Implementation of ABS – what someone utilising the genetic material has to do to comply with ABS – is not standardised across the signatory countries, leading to confusion. Could a common network solution facilitate trust and transparency? There is also a lack of common understanding of what a scientist has to do in order to adhere to the core requirements of ABS, let-alone any country-specific requirements.

How can we move towards a stronger model of traceability from sample to published data? How can we improve integration with external bioinformatic resources? The

discussions on these coalesced around a need to have standardised metadata adopted by biobanks and culture collections, to allow interoperability of their information.

Where material held in a biobank or culture collection is sold for commercial purposes, how and who should deal with ABS (and later, BBNJ)? For ABS it is the *utiliser* of the material that requires a permit, not those who collect or store that material: however, the metadata of that material as held by the biobank/culture collection will need to include information such as latitude, longitude, depth, and possibly information about any permits obtained for the sampling/collection/processing of that material, so that the eventual utiliser can understand what they do/not have to do with respect to ABS. *As stated in Sec. 3.5, eDNAqua-Plan will limit its work to recommendations on metadata necessary for ABS and BBNJ.*

An interesting point regarding ABS was raised: where a country does not have the resources to trace permits – to see if any benefits need to be shared – there can be a reluctance to issue any permits at all, unless the work is done entirely inside that country: this, however, also depends on that country having the resources to store and process that material, which is also not always the case. *A more secure, enforceable way to trace permits could be considered by the CBD.*

4.3.5. Networks, collaboration, and future outlook

Many biobanks already participate in international networks. This raises further questions about how we can strengthen European collaboration in aquatic and biodiversity biobanks or what role we should play in conservation policies, climate resilience, and biotechnology.

It was pointed out that changing the data model used by any biobank or culture collection would be a significant undertaking. Rather than changing their databases and (internally-used) standards, it is better to map their data model and ontologies onto a common standard (see Sec. 4.3.2). To lower the hurdle for uptake, it was suggested that a conversion tool (which would necessarily need to be fine-tuned to each organisation) could be collaboratively co-developed.

Those organisations that do not get any revenue from commercial activities may struggle to obtain the resources to enact the eDNAqua-Plan landscaping recommendations. They often lie at the base of the provenance chain, and as such it is incredibly important that cultures, strains, specimens, etc are well documented, accessible, findable. Collaboration could help lower the cost of work to be done. Is there some other way that they can be rewarded?

For research purposes, there are networks of biobanks:

- [GGBN](#)⁷⁷ that is working with GBIF, and have addressed the Nagoya requirements.
- At the European Level (JRC), there is the [Lucas Soil Database](#)⁷⁸ who do physical vouchering of samples.
- There was the [ECOSTAT](#)⁷⁹ project (Water Framework Directive). They want to work with reference material held by ISPRA (Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research).
- And DISSCO (Distributed System of Scientific Collections) was mentioned by several participants.

Perhaps eDNAqua-Plan should look at aligning with these initiatives to solve some of the problems discussed in this workshop: perhaps solutions already exist.

A suggestion was made to learn from COVID: at first, all the different hospitals had their own reference materials, but now they are all stored centrally at JRC. Maybe we can investigate how this was achieved, and we can draw some lessons from it? However, it is probably not feasible to do this kind of centralisation of biobanks across the heterogeneous sample types, *but* it could be good to centralise per sample type. If we can reach a consensus on how to sample, analyse and archive samples in a standardised way, this would already be a good achievement and speed things up.

The uptake of DNA components to biobanks and culture collections is gaining a lot of momentum. One participant sent out a questionnaire as part of the ECOSTAT project: 20 member states reported that they are not yet using eDNA data but they do see the need for it and plan to adopt it in the near future. Germany is organising this and leading it.

4.4. Taxonomic systems, catalogues, and concepts

Breakout C sessions were for biobanks, culture collections, and to discuss issues of taxonomic concepts and how to deal with and report on those. The [discussion topics](#)⁸⁰ focussed on the recommendations from the landscaping report made for these stakeholders, looking at what does not work well right now and how to move to the future landscape. In this section we focus on the discussions around taxonomy.

⁷⁷ https://www.ggbn.org/ggbn_portal/site/wf?p=What_is_GGBN

⁷⁸ <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-2009-topsoil-data>

⁷⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/IST-2000-26189/fr>

⁸⁰

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bjiZgFHgStKw8ol8tsbjbislmhj8oecB8F56h1kg_8/edit?usp=sharing

4.4.1 Background

A taxonomic backbone is a dynamic, central classification system for species that acts as a single, consistent reference for biodiversity data. It links accepted names to synonyms and variations, providing a foundation for integrating different datasets, resolving name discrepancies, and ensuring data consistency across scientific research, conservation, and data management platforms.

Having a taxonomic backbone is a strong enabler, but it was acknowledged that it is not trivial to provide and maintain. Challenges to establishing such a backbone include the inherent heterogeneity of biobanks and culture collections, which encompass an immense taxonomic diversity ranging from microorganisms to complex macroorganisms. Given that these repositories often operate under different institutional mandates and utilise diverse classification criteria, the integration of their data remains a formidable task. Currently, the community is far from achieving a fully-unified and globally-accepted taxonomy. This gap has sparked an ongoing debate regarding the methodologies required to harmonise these systems, highlighting that the path toward unification is not merely a technical hurdle but a complex process of scientific consensus-seeking that must account for the evolving nature of biological nomenclature and the specific needs of diverse stakeholders

4.4.2 Discussion

We agreed that having an organisation that would work with the different taxonomic backbones, to bring them together, would be a strong asset for the community to facilitate the correct use of, and mappings between, backbones (see Sec. 4.2.4 for discussions on mapping taxonomic systems). Several organisations want their taxonomic backbones to be the dominant one, which is slowing progress.

The [GBIF taxonomy](#)⁸¹ backbone is linked to multiple databases and is very stable, and so it could be used as an intermediary. It maps to over one hundred taxonomies including: Catalogue of Life, WoRMS, NCBI Taxon and PR2. One suggestion is to use the GBIF taxonomy to bridge any two ontologies that may not have been explicitly mapped e.g. WoRMS and PR2. The need for a set of guidelines for the taxonomic backbone mapping was expressed by multiple participants. Ideally, a system that allows mappings between taxonomies should also be able to accommodate (inform on) the differences between the names/related information in those systems.

N.B. *There is a mapping between WoRMS and NCIB's taxonomy, and both also map to other taxonomic backbones. An important question is how often these mappings are updated, how the mappings are done (what algorithms and decision trees are implemented), and how the information is conveyed to the users.*

⁸¹ <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d7dddbf4-2cf0-4f39-9b2a-bb099caae36c>

Other discussions:

- It is important to distinguish between taxonomic disagreements based on ego and those based on better scientific knowledge.
- Taxonomic disagreements can arise when there are fundamentally different approaches to classifying organisms (traditional, based on the authority of taxonomists; recent ones, based on phylogeny). It is important to not allow a rigid belief in one over the other system to result in confusion for those communities that need to use the eventual taxonomic names and classifications in their data.
- Capturing and allowing querying of the taxonomy synonyms (including those of different languages) was agreed to be important. A backbone needs to use the nomenclature from the component taxonomic resources. Furthermore, there are discrepancies between general and local/regional taxonomies, for example in what a species or sub-species actually is. This is a significant challenge: different regional groups of scientists have varying interpretations of what a species is. Indigenous namings should also be accommodated ([CARE](#)⁸² principles).
- The participants had differing opinions on the degree of species harmonisation precision needed in taxonomic backbones, with the prevailing opinion that there needs to be interpretation flexibility.

There was a post-meeting discussion with EurOBIS, focused on the topic of mappings between DNA-based taxonomic systems and traditional ones. There is a clear need for these mappings to be able to accommodate DNA-based occurrences in biodiversity databases that contain the whole gamut of other types of occurrences. Translating “DNA” based taxonomic names (e.g. from NCBI) to “traditional names” (e.g. from WoRMS), while working with differences in naming and classification approaches, in the spelling of names, etc., is a burden currently borne by the data providers who have to manually map their names in one system to names in another. This is a blocker, in particular where an eDNA dataset can contain hundreds of occurrences. Providing tools to automate this mapping is a priority for the user community, but it is not necessarily a priority for the data infrastructures within the resources they currently have.

A key recommendation of eDNAqua-Plan is that all taxonomic backbones should have identifiers that allow linking the species name with the interpretation (see also Sec. [5.1](#) on providing Howtos on this subject).

⁸² <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

5. Key take-home points from the workshop

This Blueprint workshop was extremely productive, and we heard from participants from all parts of the eDNA digital ecosystem that eDNAqua-Plan is investigating and which the Blueprint of Task 5.1 will consider. Here we summarise the most important requests, recommendations, issues, topics, and considerations of the workshop.

In the sections that follow, we gather together the most frequently and passionately made comments, requests, and recommendations. The stakeholders which we believe are best placed to consider these are written at the very top of each section.

We would like to include here two particularly insightful comments made:

If we make sure we have the right standards and formats, others can build the tools. We have to make sure that published data is in the right format, and tools can bring them to the right places.

We could be bold enough to state that we vote for tax-paid open and FAIR repositories and not to privatise.

There was a consensus that both long-term thinking and funding was needed to improve the current situation to improve the interoperability and smooth operation of the eDNA digital ecosystem. Much of the effort in maintaining elements of the ecosystem: reference libraries, taxonomic classification, curation, bioinformatics coding is by volunteers.

5.1. Guidelines and recommendations for data submitters

Recommendations for all stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem, but in particular

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and eDNA workflows, tools and services*
- *those with expertise and who work in exposing data using web-friendly technology*
- *stakeholders engaged in eDNA monitoring and taxonomic “backbones”*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs, EOSC Nodes*

When discussing what does not work well in the current landscape, the need for more user-friendly, practical, HowTo-type guidelines and recommendations was repeatedly highlighted. Topics mentioned were:

10. **How to navigate the eDNA digital ecosystem:** what is this “ecosystem”, what are its nodes, how do they connect to each other, what is my role in this, how can the ecosystem help me, and how can I find my way around it?
11. **How to publish my data:** for data creators (from individual scientists to organisations and commercial enterprises): where and how should I publish

my data, how do I deal with my different types of data, what standards and formats should I use, which metadata are important.

12. **A guide to eDNA data for biologists without an omics background:** what are the different types of genomic data and what are their relative strengths and weaknesses, for what type of analyses can they be used, what information are important to provide/understand when publishing/reusing omics data?
13. **A guide to how to use data technology to make your data more interoperable, reusable, and accessible** that is especially focussed on the less well-resourced organisations and regions, where employing data technicians is not an option. Two examples mentioned were about how to create URIs for digital objects – taxonomic names and biobanks and culture collection IDs.
14. **Guides to formatting your data and ensuring you have the correct metadata when publishing your data**, complemented with a catalogue of the data templates and the tools available to help. These guidelines would need to be specific to the data types and data infrastructures doing the publishing. While such documentation *is* published by those data infrastructures, it is also clear that these are somehow not finding their audience.
15. **A guide to taxonomic curation** – recommended practices.
16. **Recommendations for collecting good (meta)data** as your experiment proceeds and during the different stages of the data life cycle and for different types of data. This is essentially training – see Sec. 3.1 – but where that training is accompanied by HowTo reference material and checklists.
17. **A registry of data brokers in Europe.** Data brokers act as an intermediary between the data submitters and the data repositories, and as such not only provide information about where to publish data, but help you to do it.

From further discussion, it was clear that these should be created with the following in mind:

- **User friendly** To be effective, they should incorporate diagrams, flowcharts, or decision trees that supplement blocks of text. The key point is that scientists do not (feel they) have the time to read documentation as well as actually publish the data.
- **These should not be linked to a particular project** as this limits their findability. One obvious recommendation is to use [EDITO](https://www.edito.eu/)⁸³, which is promoted as a core European Digital Twin infrastructure and hence likely to offer a sustainable location, to be a well-advertised and -used platform; and being connected to many data sources and VREs, can also offer opportunities for integrating guidelines and recommendations with tools and templates (see Sec. 5.3 and 5.4). Another possibility would be with [GeoBON](https://geobon.org/)⁸⁴ and/or Omic BON (which is associated with GeoBON). INSDC databases would seem to be

⁸³ <https://www.edito.eu/>

⁸⁴ <https://geobon.org/>

a natural home for DNA documentation, and GBIF and OBIS for DNA-biodiversity documentation. Wherever they are, with good search engine optimisation, this information can be found wherever it is published.

- **Community endorsed/approved** Endorsement by the data infrastructures and scientific community improves uptake and credibility.
- **Open for contributions** They should be open for contributions by anyone, and updatable with version control, as that improves sustainability and continued relevance.
- **Good promotion** “Advertise” the guidelines via publications in a journal (among other channels) to come to the attention of the scientific community, and it adds an aura of authority and approval.

Most of the data infrastructures that are part of the eDNA digital ecosystem *do* provide documentation, manuals and templates, and many of these are comprehensive and well written. Why are these not being found and/or understood? It would be good to investigate this, as a lot of time and effort goes into creating documentation. It may be the case that the scientists do not have, or do not believe they have, the time to read comprehensive documentation or to take courses to learn how to format and submit data for publication. If so, why is that? We also suggest that engaging pedagogical expertise in the design of the documentation would be worth consideration.

5.2. Metadata checklists/schemas, to filter on data for particular purposes

Recommendations for

- *data infrastructures that provide data publication services*
- *stakeholders that provide and run (e)DNA workflows, from samples through to bioinformatics*
- *stakeholders engaged in eDNA monitoring (to provide input to the checklists/schemas)*
- *ERICs and RIs (to provide input or created their own checklists/schemas)*

There is a frustrating clash of desires when it comes the richness, formatting, and quantity of metadata provided along with or contained within published data: there was a clear demand for more mandatory, interoperable, and accessible metadata linked to samples, sequences, taxonomic names, and bioinformatics; however, all of the data infrastructures at the meeting stated that they do not want to strengthen the demands already made on their (meta)data – because (i) when they do, data submissions drop, and (ii) of a lack of resources to do even more curation, in particular where they deal with data from different domains of science with different requirements. We also add, wryly, that the scientists asking for more metadata are often the same scientists who are submitting the data (lacking sufficient metadata) in the first place.

How can one work around this? From the workshop discussions, it appears that part of the problem from the scientists point-of-view is that submitting data is already a confusing, frustrating, and lengthy process: if this could be made easier, for example via tools, better documentation, better data training, and the employers giving the scientists the time to submit data, then this part of the problem would be resolved.

However, all of this will take time, and there will still be a great deal of “historical” data (anything published before the current date) that will not be improved. A suggestion, first made at a previous WP3 workshop and discussed during this workshop, was to *create metadata checklists or schemas which are built around particular data purposes and which can help users find quality data*: for data to be suitable for some purpose, what information need to be available and what format/standards should that information have? Here we are talking about information either in the metadata that describes a data set, or for the case of the DwC-A format, the information within those DwC files (i.e. the columns in the CSVs that make up DwC-A). Two examples: where data are to be used to look for invasive species, then a specific location, a date, and a species name are absolutely necessary; where latitude, longitude, date and depth are provided, users will be able to check on whether ABS obligations apply. If users could filter on data according to such checklists/schemas, then they would not need to do that themselves a-posteriori, saving time and effort. (N.B. this is about the quantity and standardisation of the metadata, not the correctness of the values.)

In general the feedback to this idea was positive. It was pointed out that such checklists/schemas would not only be useful for filtering on data to download and work with, but would also be useful for people wanting to create and submit data, to know what they need to include if the data were to be useful for some purpose (possibly including the purpose for which they were gathered). Key here will be to develop good checklists/schemas that are easy to find, implement, update, understand, and are correct in their content. It will also be necessary to take on board that data of different types – different types of omics data as well as (possibly) different types of biodiversity data – may require different specifics.

INSDC have a form of such checklists for sample metadata with [packages+extensions at NCBI](#)⁸⁵ and [checklists at ENA](#)⁸⁶. The APIs allow one to search for which “checklist” was used to submit the data and most of that above-mentioned minimal metadata. These checklists are relatively generic however, e.g. “GSC MlxS Water”, so do not explicitly have a “purpose”. A caveat to the proposed approach is that having too many checklists creates maintenance and querying complexity, and can make it confusing for the data submitters. eDNAqua-Plan will create some checklists and will aim to discuss these with the

⁸⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/docs/packages/>

⁸⁶ <https://ena-browser-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/browser/sample-checklists.html>

concerned data infrastructures (GBIF, OBIS, PANGAEA, ENA, for example). Some “purposes” could be: MSFD and WFD monitoring, Invasive species detection, GOOS biological EOVs (although these do not yet include eDNA), ecosystem/community analysis, as well as a “eDNAqua-Plan gold star” standard.

5.3 Training and tools

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and eDNA workflows, tools and services*
- *stakeholders that train and engage scientists in research (e.g. universities)*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs, EOSC Nodes*

There is a clear need for training on FAIR data and data management for eDNA-related data, as the level of data literacy among scientists and technicians is generally quite low. An understanding not only of what to do, but why it is important, and how it contributes to (more) science (happening) needs is lacking. Both individual scientists and universities need to understand where they stand in the digital ecosystem, and how they can (should) contribute to it.

There are, in fact, many training courses and webinars on FAIR data/management, bioinformatics, etc – the [EMBL](https://www.embl.org/training/)⁸⁷ and [EMBRC](https://www.embrc.eu/marine-training/)⁸⁸ training platforms to name only two. However, the primary source of training for scientists and technicians should be the university courses they take to become qualified, and coverage of good data training – covering FAIR data, data management, Open science – is patchy over the European institutions. Our take-home points are:

- **It is the responsibility of the institutions** employing the scientists and technicians to **provide the necessary training**, either directly themselves or by requiring/allowing their employees to follow external courses.
- **It is the responsibility of the scientists and technicians** themselves to **understand that they need this training**, and to take them.
- **The push** to get that training, and the space to be allowed to take the training, **needs to come from above**, not below.

As well as training, tools to help those data creators to make their data interoperable, to format, to add the necessary metadata, should be created and provided.

- **We recommend electronic notebooks** as an excellent tool for use by scientists and technicians working in the eDNA ecosystem. These should not only record data but also: add semantic annotation, ensure the necessary metadata are collected so that the data can later be published, ensure links between related data and metadata can be made (provenance), and ideally also allow data to be exported in the formats required by the target data

⁸⁷ <https://www.embl.org/training/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.embrc.eu/marine-training/>

infrastructures. They would be a cost-effective and painless (for the scientists) way to ensure compliance with checklists, e.g. those required by data infrastructures such as ENA, the FAIRe ones, etc.

The responsibility for providing tools is on the organisations employing the scientists and technicians, however projects (e.g. Horizon) and RIs and ERICs could also play a practical role here. Clearly the various data infrastructures working with omics and biodiversity should – and do – provide tools. These are often (understandably) focussed on their particular data requirements, setting some limits on their general usability.

To make these tools and training materials more widely findable, **it was suggested that they be catalogued in a sustainable, central, and obvious place**. The same suggestions made in Sec. 5.1 can be made here: [EDITO](#)⁸⁹, [GeoBON](#)⁹⁰ and/or Omic BON.

5.4 Standardisation and interoperability

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and provide, create, or run eDNA workflows, tools and services (including individual scientists)*
- *stakeholders that train and engage scientists in research (e.g. universities)*
- *RIs and ERICs, EOSC Nodes*

Standardisation of terminology

eDNA data include many types: sequences, taxonomic tables, biodiversity datasets, reference species and sequences, etc, and the vocabularies to use will differ between these. One scientist may create data that need to be submitted to different data infrastructures, and they find it confusing when the terminology, as well as the formatting and data file standards, differ from one dataset to another. A strong request for more standardisation over the digital ecosystem was made.

In summary, the following were suggested:

- **Adopt common terminology** (vocabulary/ontology) for common data types (to then be used in the metadata describing data and the metadata within data).
 - Where a vocabulary is used then use it exactly as recommended by the maintainer (spelling, formatting, and definition): do not “personalise”.
 - Have an easy help desk (coupled to an FAQ) for users to raise questions (e.g. GitHub issues, as this is already used by many).

⁸⁹ <https://www.edito.eu/>

⁹⁰ <https://geobon.org/>

- However, the fact remains that where different organisations maintain different vocabularies, different naming conventions *will* happen. Additionally, where different organisations use the same vocabularies, differences can creep in where their needs from or for their data differ. However, the mindset should be to avoid pluralism for its own sake. We suggest **mappings between vocabularies/ontologies** would help diminish the frustration (see also Sec. [5.5](#)), and Europe could help by providing for a centralised publisher and maintainer of community-recommended vocabularies.
 - These mappings could also provide input to the standards maintainers and users, to show where deviations are getting large.
 - The mappings should be easily findable.
 - They will need to be maintained so they remain current.
 - To be sustainable and useful, the organisations maintaining and using the vocabularies should be involved in creating these mappings.
 - Sharing the necessary information in a way that machines can find, read, and understand will make the mapping process and maintenance easier.

(Meta)data

Recommendations regarding templates for collecting research data and/or metadata are:

- **Make it easy to find your templates** to be used to format data for publication.
- **Templates should** be constructed such that they can **be used almost on their own** to format data for submission are key to engaging the data submitters.
- **Provide templates that are complete**, and provide an example for every aspect of any data file, not only the mandatory and strongly recommended parts.
- The expressed desire to have only one data standard and one associated template is clearly not feasible for *all* data. To mitigate the confusion felt by the scientists when trying to format data, we suggest **greater use of data brokerage services**. Data brokers could help the scientists by providing a one-stop-shop for data publication. Additionally, where **machine-interoperable lines of communication are made between brokers and data infrastructures** regarding the data templates, metadata requirements, vocabularies used, etc, then any changes from the data infrastructures can be quickly picked up and acted on by the brokers.

Bioinformatics

Regarding bioinformatics, these specific recommendations were made:

- **Bioinformatics: FASTQ, FASTA, and taxonomic (OTU, ASV tables) are only semi-standardised:**
 - Taxonomic (OTU, ASV tables) are all text files (usually CSV, TSV, although often also XLSX), and they look very similar, but there are no defined standards. This should be corrected: for these files to be interoperable and connected to the rest of the digital ecosystem, there should be strong recommendations regarding the formatting of the data within these files. It is suggested that TDWG standardises and maintains the ASVs/taxonomic table format.
 - FASTQ/FASTA - [GA4GH](https://www.ga4gh.org/)⁹¹ is the maintainer of FASTQ, CRAM and BAM formats, and they could extend this to include a better standardisation (to make the data machine2machine interoperable) of the data *within* those formats, and to bring FASTA under their wing.
- **Metadata checklists and templates should be developed and encouraged/enforced.** This includes sample collection, sequence experiment metadata.
 - *There is an activity being planned to improve the metadata and data flow from ENA to GBIF. The aim is to increase the occurrence records shared, ensure that they are relevant and to map more of the metadata to the DwC and DNA extension standard used by GIF. The priorities are currently being set before work can begin.*
- See Sec. [5.10](#) for other recommendations regarding bioinformatics.

5.5 Stronger metadata requirements

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and provide, create, or run eDNA workflows, tools and services (including individual scientists)*
- *stakeholders that train and engage scientists in research (e.g. universities)*
- *RIs and ERICs, EOSC Nodes*

There was a very clear statement made for more mandatory metadata (discovery and description metadata, and metadata as embedded in data), to make datasets more useful, and to be able to judge their usefulness before any scientific analysis is done.

As reported in Sec. [5.2](#), there are opposing forces at play: making too many demands on (meta)data is something data infrastructures do not like to do, but the result is often data with poor provenance. Additionally, the onus is on each data user to each filter data on their own (often very similar) requirements – a repeating of often the same efforts. eDNAqua-Plan, the community, the data infrastructures can all suggest as-minimal-as-possible mandatory metadata, we can all also suggest

⁹¹ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

work-arounds (such as the checklists/schemas of Sec [5.2](#)), **but the best way to sustainably ensure good metadata is for the scientists and technicians to have sufficient data literacy, time, training, and tools (Secs [5.1](#), [5.3](#)), helping them format, publish, and describe data sufficiently. *That is the main bottleneck in the process.***

In eDNAqua-Plan we will be making recommendations concerning metadata for different parts of the eDNA digital ecosystem in our deliverables. **Any development regarding metadata requirements should be made with the data infrastructures,** as otherwise they will not get taken up and will not be sustainable.

It was also requested that when metadata corrections are identified – by whomever – that the process to correct/update those was as timely as possible. While many data infrastructures are reluctant to change the metadata they are given (these are not their metadata but rather belong to the data provider), but it was suggested that **corrections to metadata could be flagged as such, to allow the original and the new values to be both findable at the same time.**

Some specific information were suggested for published data

- Mandatory: PCR primers to be accessible along with the sequence data they apply to
- Mandatory: protocols, and moreover such that they are accessible (i.e. as a URI/DOI rather than just a name)
- Mandatory (for field-obtained samples): ABS compliance information, including latitude and longitude
- Strongly recommended: environmental/habitat terms, moreover taken from controlled vocabularies and provided as URIs

To this, eDNAqua-Plan adds

- Contributors to the data: so they can be acknowledged, and hence encouraged, to publish data (see Sec. [5.7](#))
- (Open access) related publications and datasets: so the scope of the data can be assessed, and extra information can be obtained
- eDNAqua-Plan also supports the recommendations in the [FAIRe](#)⁹² checklist

It was also suggested that providing a way for scientists to feed back their filtered data (alternatively, their filtering code/methods) to the data infrastructures would be a way for the community of data users to help each other, and if credit (e.g. via ORCID) could be given for doing so, this would encourage uptake.

Regarding **data that are produced by instruments, devices, and sensors that are used at marine and aquatic stations/labs:** where these produce data that are interoperable (and open), it is much easier for the scientists to work with and

⁹² <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

eventually publish those data. This is not always the case, and effort to push this could be made. For this, one should not ask these enterprises to output their data into the specific formats that are used by our community, today: standards change with time, and many instruments and sensors are used by different communities with different standards. However, **if at least there were metadata accompanying and describing the data were semantically annotated and interoperable**, e.g. in JSON-LD, this would have enormous benefits.

We note that the marine research and monitoring community is not as important as the biomedical community for these companies.

For biobanks and culture collections, we should all be aware that these hold samples and their metadata that can go back decades, centuries even. For some, the metadata are still written on paper that still need to be digitised. The specificity of some of those metadata (e.g. locations) will be much lower than required in our modern times; additionally, as geographic names change with time, some location names may no longer exist. *Perhaps there is something to learn from those who manage historical document collections?*

Curation

Curation of (meta)data is key to the quality of those (meta)data. The workshop participants recommended that both data creators (scientists) and data infrastructures that publish the data should be considered responsible for data curation. It was stressed that it is not the role of data infrastructures to go as far as data interpretation, as this may risk data integrity and trustability. **However, without plenty of well-formatted, understandable, and useful metadata, it will always be difficult for data users to judge the quality of the data they access**, resulting in either uncertain science or throw-out (wasted) data.

It is important that all stakeholders that provide data or standards that are used in the eDNA digital ecosystem should ensure that information about their versioning, changes, additions are issued promptly, in machine-accessible formats. This will allow for a smoother and more up-to-date digital ecosystem.

Primer metadata

While information about the primers used for any sequence published should be mandatory to provide, one suggestion for filling this information gap was to create and maintain a unifying platform which can suggest primers for specific taxonomic groups/purposes, protocols, repositories. If this can be maintained sustainably, it could become a standard reference and result in greater uniformisation of primer methodology.

5.6 AI / LLM

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and provide, create, or run eDNA workflows, tools and services (including individual scientists)*
- *stakeholders that create and maintain controlled vocabularies / ontologies*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs, EOSC Nodes*

Several interesting suggestions concerning the use of AI to help improve the eDNA digital ecosystem were made.

- To assist in the work of mapping vocabularies (see Sec [5.4](#))
- To check the formatting of data, its conformity to a template, use of vocabularies, and general interoperability, before data are submitted to be published
- To search for the information to add to newly-created metadata fields (in the discovery and description metadata as well as in the data itself) for the “historical” data (i.e. everything published before the new requirements were made)
- To find and add semantics (terms from vocabularies)

5.7 The importance of publishing data

Recommendations for all stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem, but in particular

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and provide, create, or run eDNA workflows, tools and services (including individual scientists)*
- *stakeholders that train and engage scientists in research (e.g. universities)*
- *publishers of science journals*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs, EOSC Nodes*

The rewards for publishing data should be greater, as this will encourage the publishing of those data. Recommendations are:

- **Electronic tracking of published data:** to make it mandatory to include the ORCID for the data creator, and ensure that the information about this can be harvested by/transmitted to ORCID (whether the data are assigned a DOI or only a URI). It should also be easy to list and credit (via their ORCIDs) all data contributors: these can be numerous, and to have to manually enter each is a discouragement.
- While ORCID does distinguish between different work types (e.g. publications vs. data), it would be a greater inducement to doing this if these different works were grouped by category and easily linkable to a CV/resume.
- **Where public money is used to do research, it should be mandatory that *all research outputs are made open***, and a system to help do and to check this is done should be in place. Universities and other publicly-funded

organisations, and their employees, should be judged on the data they produce as much as the articles. The mindset should be that data are as important as articles, and moreover that data should be published in open access repositories. **Electronic tracking of published data via mandatory acknowledgement of the funder** is recommended, and ensuring that this information can be harvested, for example by their EDMO or ROR IDs.

- **Specialised data should be published in specialist repositories.** This is a general recommendation of eDNAqua-Plan as the data are then more findable, and usually more accessible and interoperable. This means that universities should not archive the data themselves (except for proprietary, sensitive, or unusual data), but instead catalogue them with links to where they are made accessible.
- **Institute a d-index (d for data),** equivalent to the h-index used to measure a researcher's output and impact based on their scholarly publications.
- When (meta)data are harvested between repositories, it should be mandatory that the original DOI/URL, citation, and funder and data creators/contributors fields are also reproduced.
- Many parties are still reluctant to share sequence data from their local biodiversity, because they are **worried that this could result in misuse** of the data or misuse of nature? **Clear guidelines** for how this is dealt with by the data infrastructures is required, for example explaining how to embargo or hide sensitive data, as well as their policies for data sharing.

Recommendations for scientific journals are:

- **Data statements should be mandatory,** and they should provide the **DOI/URIs** of the published data produced by the experiment. Moreover, journals should **recommend specialist repositories** for specialist data, and generalist ones only for data that fall “out of scope”.
- To allow for better tracking of data creators, the **funder fields** should be **mandatory for a DOI**, as should be the **online PID** of the funder (ROR, EDMO) and data creator and contributors (ORCID).
- The **reproducibility** of results, including the use and accessibility of the data and pipelines used in the scientific work, could be included as a general **part of the peer review process**. This could also tackle the reproducibility crisis.
- **Linking data and publications:** all data infrastructures should have fields to record related data and publications, and all journals should do likewise. Machine-readable metadata are a must here; as journals do not have catalogue “metadata records”, this is probably best done via the DOI metadata handled by registries (e.g. CrossRef), which in turn would need to ensure fields to carry these information were available.

5.8 Biomonitoring

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services*
- *stakeholders that engage or are engaged in biomonitoring services*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs*

While much biomonitoring is done by universities, **agencies and companies are also engaged in performing biomonitoring**. It was pointed out that it is not always the case that the technicians doing the sampling work and those managing the resulting data have an in-depth understanding of how genomics science works, what FAIR and open data mean and require, how and where biomonitoring data are published, and what sorts of science others often do with these data: and this should be taken on board when creating recommendations and writing documentation. While companies can be made enthusiastic about sharing data (in cooperation with their customers), **the approach to take, how to explain what to do, and recommendations to make should be tailored for this particular audience**.

Biomonitoring done under national mandates will almost certainly have to be deposited on a national level. Unfortunately, national-level repositories are often less FAIR and less open (in particular those for inland waters). If there was a requirement that at least all the repository-level discovery and description metadata for these data were findable and accessible (by anyone), and interoperable and reusable (using standards, adding provenance metadata), that would be a first step to opening up these often siloed data.

5.9 Provenance

Recommendations for all stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem, but in particular

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and provide, create, or run eDNA workflows, tools and services (including individual scientists)*
- *stakeholders that train and engage scientists in research (e.g. universities)*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs*

Provenance is about providing trustability, traceability, reusability. Unfortunately, provenance is generally poorly provided in the eDNA digital ecosystem, with gaps in information coverage and non-accessible references. **The responsibility to improve the provenance models for the data of the eDNA digital ecosystem falls on all stakeholders**: those who create the data (collect the provenance information and ensure they include it with the data), those who provide data publications services (require provenance information, provide templates for provenance information), the organisations who fund and perform the science (make provenance an important part of published data).

It was pointed out that few templates specifically for provenance metadata exist. These would allow scientists to provide their own provenance files, for example, to supplement what is possible currently with the data infrastructures. To be findable we suggested that these could be provided by the data infrastructures, by the RIs and ERICs in the specialised domains, via or European infrastructures such as [EDITO](#)⁹³. However, whether many scientists would do that is a different question, as it would be an extra “burden” on them. See Sec. [5.3](#) for suggestions to mitigate this.

Improving overall provenance provision was not considered a priority by the participants at the workshop, **however improving the provision of certain elements of provenance was**, including primers, protocols, detailed location information, and agents involved in or funding the work. In addition, there are more fields that fall under provenance listed in the **FAIRe checklists**.

Data duplication

A related issue concerns duplication of data, which can happen both for source data (published in an original catalogue and then harvested) and derived data (the same source data is analysed and results published by several people).

- **Ensuring that all data are always accredited to an ORCID** could be one way to identify duplicates
- **Always require that source data URIs are credited** in derived data or when data are harvested.

5.10 Bioinformatics

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide data publication services and provide, create, or run eDNA workflows, tools and services*
- *stakeholders that train and engage scientists in research (e.g. universities)*
- *bioinformaticians*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs*

A recommendation to **ensure that bioinformatics workflows are published** – the code as well as the description of the code – and in a reproducible way. **Ensuring that the software published is FAIR**, following [FAIR principles for research software](#)^{R7} and the numerous FAIR recommendations (e.g. from the [FAIR-IMPACT project](#)⁹⁴), would satisfy these recommendations. This would address the case of “left behind” software: when someone develops code as part of doctoral or post-doctoral work, they often find themselves having to maintain it on a voluntary basis once they

⁹³ <https://www.edito.eu/>

⁹⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/metrics-software>

leave to their next job, or choose to leave it frozen. If those software are FAIR, then they can be found, understood, run, and potentially updated or maintained by others.

A frequent statement made is that if a scientist wishes to make a detailed check on the results of a workflow, they will re-run it themselves. This does not take into account that not everyone who uses the outputs of bioinformatics have either the expertise or the resources to do this. For the first point: it will always be the case that complex science will be difficult for non-experts to understand, **but guidelines for understanding and using omics data for non-omics experts** (Sec. 5.1) would help. **Making workflows available on (free/cheap) online environments** (e.g. [Galaxy](#)⁹⁵, [Mgnify](#)⁹⁶) would go a long way to addressing the second point.

A current gap in the eDNA digital ecosystem is the publication of ASVs (taxonomic lists output by bioinformatics). **Encouraging the publication** of these data, linked via description metadata to the bioinformatics and to the source sequences, should be a priority.

Sec. 5.4 outlines recommendations on standardising the outputs of bioinformatics – the FASTA and ASV files.

5.11 Reference libraries

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that provide reference libraries and reference library data*
- *anyone who builds a reference library for eDNA science*
- *the EC/EU and its digital research environment*
- *RIs and ERICs*

The consensus in eDNAqua-Plan is to have a **diverse portfolio of independent reference libraries**, each with their own focus. Crucially however, the **metadata should be interoperable between each other**, with a **federated metadata search engine running across them** all so that users/machines can find the appropriate data sources.

A number of recommendations concerning reference sequences and reference libraries were made:

- **Reference sequences should always be published in a public database.** This makes them available for community use.
- A greater focus should be placed on **standardising the way to create a reference database**. The alternative of cataloguing all databases and trying to make them interoperable is considered to be more work overall and less sustainable. However, it needs to be acknowledged that a standardised

⁹⁵ <https://usegalaxy.org/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics>

database will not necessarily work in all cases, in particular for species for which there is not much sequence data available. If all reference databases – from individual to global – at least signed up to the same set of (meta)data standards and data sharing methods, that would greatly improve the smoothness of this part of the digital ecosystem.

- **There is a need for a metric of completeness** of reference databases, to show where the data gaps are. Incomplete reference libraries can be a very limiting problem for the practical employment of eDNA for biomonitoring

Quality and curation

- Having a good set of essential metadata would allow for an evaluation of the taxonomic identification and hence contribute to the quality of a reference: **the curation and quality metadata should be provided by the reference library** itself. In particular, the certainty of the taxonomic names and potentially other standardised quality indicator metadata should be considered.
- **Reporting confidence levels alone is not enough**, as different tools work differently and provide different results: the type of confidence value (i.e. sequence similarity, query coverage, bootstrap confidence) is also necessary.
- **Expert curators should always be employed** to review the data, and this should include the taxonomic identification. There was concern in being able to obtain sufficient expert curators. **Acknowledgement of their work** via a “curation” metadata field is recommended (these can then be harvested by ORCID and added to their “works” – Sec Sec. [5.7](#)). Some level of **automated curation** could also be investigated.
- Could **taxonomic annotations be routinely checked between different databases, to find and reduce errors?** If the data are shared using machine-accessible methods, then once the methods are set up, the processing can be automatic.

5.12 Biobanks and culture collections

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that do biobanking*
- *culture collections, natural history museums*
- *RIs and ERICs involved in these activities*

Culture collections and biobanks are a vital, foundational, component of the eDNA ecosystem. They have unique challenges, not only associated with the fact that they handle physical material as well as data, but that they often have a very wide scope in terms of the items they store, the audience they serve, the timelines they accommodate. Different taxonomic backbones, ontologies, and standards are used for the different types of organisms, and all need to be accommodated.

Particular points are:

- **Where material held in a biobank or collection is sold for commercial purposes, how and who should deal with ABS?** An inability to trace permits can lead to countries not issuing permits, and a lack of resources to process samples in-country can also. This should be taken into account in any ABS (or later, BBNJ) recommendations, documentation, and tools.
- A very important metadatum for items in biobanks and culture collections is the sample (/strain) ID. **These need to be globally unique and persistent and ideally should be linked to URIs that make them findable and accessible online, and expose information about the item in question.** These IDs should be findable from all subsequent samples and all derived data, to allow for full track and trace from data to sample, and sample to data.
- Material taken from biobanks and collections often undergo subsequent material and data processing steps. The metadata standards used for the original sample and those used when publishing/storing subsequent samples and/or data will probably be different. This can lead to difficulties in the track and trace. **Crosswalks between the ontologies underpinning the standards should be considered.**
- A unique consideration for collections is that their “historical” items (objects and associated data) are truly historical, potentially going back hundreds of years. Digging out the information that are missing to conform to modern metadata requirements **requires expert curators, which is a human resources cost to be acknowledged.** In addition, **guidance on creating knowledge graphs that can accommodate the interpretations (the new metadata) from the information available, as well as the process of reaching those interpretations, is required.**
- Genetic and bioinformatic data now need to be integrated into the existing systems that each collection or biobank uses. Rather than asking that they change their databases and internally-used standards, it is better to **map their data models and ontologies onto a common standard that the community can co-create** (probably per collection or organism type). **A mapping tool that is created in common** would also be useful, especially for those smaller collections with fewer resources.

In all of this work, **collaboration and co-creation is necessary, in particular if we want to include the smaller collections with fewer resources.** A way to reward those taking up the work to modernise their data systems, co-create and adopt new standards, should be considered. **Networks are vitally important to improving the future outlook** with respect to (meta)data management.

5.13 Taxonomic backbones

Recommendations for

- *stakeholders that maintain and/or combine taxonomic backbones*
- *stakeholders that perform taxonomic activities*
- *RIs and ERICs involved in these activities*

Points to highlight are:

- There was discussion about **regular, documented, sustained mapping of different taxonomies to each other**. This is a recommendation of the landscaping and the workshop participants agreed with this. **Having an organisation that brings together the different taxonomic backbones**, would be a strong asset for the community to facilitate this. The GBIF backbone is linked to multiple databases and is very stable, and could be used as an intermediary.
- **Guidelines for creating and implementing mappings** should be created.
- In addition, **tools to find a name in one system from a name in another should be created**. Currently the burden on doing this falls on the data provider, and is a largely manual process (aided with APIs, but not fully tooled) which leaves room for interpretation in dealing with differences in spelling and naming convention. This is a significant blocker.
- Taxonomic backbones should **accommodate multiple (human) languages and indigenous namings**.
- It was noted that some sequences in the INSDC repositories have the wrong species identification – this is an acceptable and inevitable part of science, but the issue is that participants found it hard to get these changed → as raised above, need timely updating of metadata
- A key recommendation of eDNAqua-Plan is that **all taxonomic backbones should have identifiers that allow linking the species name with the interpretation**. On this, HowTo guides for the smaller taxonomic catalogues are required

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1: Data submission templates

For some of the larger data infrastructures among our stakeholders

Repository	Submission Templates	Comment
ENA	Sample level: https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists	
NCBI	Sample level: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/docs/packaging/	
GBIF	N/A	Need to publish data via an affiliate. Does provide the required software to publish.
EurOBIS	Webform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.eurobis.org/submit https://manual.obis.org/data_format.html#obis-holds-more-than-just-species-occurrences-the-env-data-approach 	
OBIS	https://manual.obis.org/data_format.html#obis-holds-more-than-just-species-occurrences-the-env-data-approach	
PANGAEA	Templates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Best_practice_manuals_and_templates https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Biology 	
MGNIFY	(as for ENA)	Submit sequence to ENA
BioSample	(as for ENA and NCBI)	See ENA and NCBI. (There are also several non-INSDC BioSample checklists for non-sequence related

Repository	Submission Templates	Comment
		resources, which have fewer minimum requirements)

Supplementary Table 2: Essential Reference Library metadata concepts presented at the workshop (early draft)

Metadata Category	Metadata field	Metadata detail
PRE-BARCODE METADATA	Specimen identifier	unique voucher number, strain ID, or specimen code
	Repository / collection	e.g., museum, culture collection, field station
	Sample type	environmental/specimen/culture
	Date of collection	
	Geographic origin	latitude, longitude, locality, country, and water body for marine samples
	Habitat / environment type	e.g., pelagic, benthic, soil, host-associated - need defined list?
	Depth / altitude, temperature, and/or salinity	when relevant
	Specimen identification	taxonomic name linked to specimen by person who identified it
	Original identification method	morphological, molecular, or both
BARCODE PROCESSING METADATA	Sequence accession number	
	Source database name?	GenBank, ENA, BOLD, PR2, etc.
	Source database version?	
	Marker / gene region	e.g., 18S, COI, rbcL, ITS
	Sequence length	
	Sequencing platform?	
	Quality metrics	e.g., % ambiguous bases, Phred score - defined list?
	trimming details?	
	Quality control notes	e.g., chimera check, contamination screening
	Link to associated publication	
CURATION METADATA	Curation status	raw, expert-reviewed
	Curator / expert validator name + date of curation	+ institute / contact details?
	Date of expert validation	
	Curation method	phylogeny, cluster, etc. - need defined list?
	Ranking/confidence level method	obligatory? defined list?
	Ranking/confidence level score	obligatory?

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

